

SMART ERA

D6.2 Synthesis of policy audits in pilot regions

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Acronyms

Acronym	Title
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
BiH	Bosnia and Herzegovina
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CF	Cohesion Fund
CLLD	Community-Led Local Development
DESI	Digital Economy and Society Index
DG AGRI	Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development
DG REGIO	Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EIS	European Innovation Scoreboard
EMFAF	European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESF+	European Social Fund+
EU	European Union
EUSAIR	EU Strategy for the Adriatic and Ionian Region
EUSALP	European Union Strategy for the Alpine Region
FAMENET	Fisheries and Aquaculture Monitoring, Evaluation and Local Support Network
FLAG	Fisheries Local Action Group
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
ITI	Integrated Territorial Instrument
JTF	Just Transition Fund
KM	Bosnian mark
LAG	Local Action Group
LEADER	Liaison Entre Actions pour le Développement des Economies Rurales
LTVRA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
O	Output
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OP	Operational Programme
PNRR	Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (National Plan for Recovery and Resilience)
PPS	Purchasing Power Standard
R	Result
R&D	Research and Development
RIS	Regional Innovation Scoreboard

Executive Summary

SMART ERA is a Horizon Europe project (*Smart community-led transition for Europe's rural areas*) whose aim is to bolster rural resilience by co-designing innovative solutions. These solutions are multi-sectoral and multi-actor, meaning that they are co-designed, co-created and co-implemented with a diversity of local actors.

This report provides the findings from the SMART ERA **analysis of policy framework supporting community-led rural innovation** (also referred to as 'smart rural areas/communities') at the European level and within the project's case study countries (Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Finland, Italy, Slovenia, Spain).

This report investigates and assesses the plethora of policy frameworks enabling or hindering community-led innovations in these rural areas. Relations among actors and their resistance or support to community transition is also analysed.

Chapter 1 and **2** open this document by setting the basis and underlying hypothesis accompanying this study, as well as outlining the methodology and materials that have been used to develop it.

Chapter 3 focusses on the EU-level concepts and policies linked to community-led innovation.

Chapter 4 provides more in-depth analysis from the SMART ERA Pilot regions, both at the national level and territorial level (regional or sub-regional accordingly with the Pilots).

Chapter 5 compares the findings from the project's Pilot countries, as well as the EU-level findings. On one hand, these outputs allow to scope out from the specificity of each case as to look at the broader picture. On the other hand, this chapter compares the EU-level policy framework and its practical execution, hence highlighting strengths, gaps and inconsistencies.

Chapter 6 is the conclusive fragment of this report. It presents the conclusions and avenues for future research.

1. Introduction

Europe's **narrative** around rural areas has shifted. Once seen as peripheral places needing compensatory measures, they are now increasingly recognised as areas of opportunities and resources that can drive Europe's future¹². This **eye-opening** is grounded on reality as data shows that over 70% of Europe's renewable energy taking place in rural areas³, and rural areas are major guardian to cultural and natural capital, including water resources, critical raw materials, ecosystem services and traditional knowledge.

While this change in perspective is a major achievement, significant challenges and gaps remain. First, the new narrative is **not always supported by ambitious or coherent policy frameworks**. Although rural areas are increasingly seen as places of opportunity, several policies, funding programs, and the overall policy structure are still place-blind⁴. The impact of several EU and national policies leads to **territorial inequalities**. Tools like Territorial Impact Assessments and rural proofing are far from being fully implemented or mainstreamed across the EU and within national policies of the EU-27.

Second, despite the positive shift in narrative and some progress towards its implementation, **rural communities are still feeling like left behind**. The so-called "geography of discontent" reveals that many rural residents feel unheard and believe their only way to act is by voting for extremist or EU-sceptic parties.

This report focuses on rural communities themselves. It explores how they can take initiative and smartly organise to plan their own development o-designing and implementing innovative solutions tailored to their unique challenges and opportunities.

To do this, we examine **six case studies** from the SMART ERA Pilot Regions, located in five EU Member States and one non-EU country. For each region, we analyse the local and context and explore the dynamics that help or hinder progress toward smarter rural development. Our analysis focusses on **policy and stakeholder-interactions**, as cross-cutting enabling condition to allow for innovation in rural areas and its scaling-up.

We also consider broader **EU-level conditions and policy frameworks** that either support or block the smart rural transition. In conclusion, this report reflects on the lessons learned from comparing these case studies with the wider EU context. It provides practical policy options and recommendations to better use policy tools in support of smart rural areas.

¹ European Commission (2023). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions A long-term Vision for the EU's Rural Areas - Towards stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous rural areas by 2040.

² OECD (2020). Rural Well-being. Geography of Opportunity.

³ Castillo, C. P., Barranco, R. R., Curtale, R., Kompil, M., Jacobs-Crisioni, C., Rodriguez, S. V., Aurambout, J., Silva, F. B. E., Sulis, P., & Auteri, D. (2023). Are remote rural areas in Europe remarkable? Challenges and opportunities. *Journal Of Rural Studies*, 105, 103180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.103180>

⁴ OECD (2025). *Place-Based Policies for the Future*.

2. Materials and Methods

This analysis was performed by the European Association for Innovation in Local Development (AEIDL) in close cooperation with SMART ERA Pilot Regions (Pilot Orchestrators and Community Activators). It applies to the SMART ERA Policy Audit Methodology⁵, developed specifically for this project but replicable for the policy audit of other rural communities.

The EU-level analysis was coordinated by AEIDL and grounded on the review of existing policy reports and policy documents. Please note that this report builds on previous projects⁶ and publications^{7,8,9}. We use the terms “community-led rural innovation” and “smart rural areas” interchangeably, as both refer to innovation driven by communities for the broader benefit of their territories and society. Smart rural communities are those that leverage their strengths and assets to meet local needs, improve resilience, and enhance wellbeing.

The analysis of Pilot Regions and of their respective country’s policy frameworks hence follow a multi-step approach led by Pilot Orchestrators and Community Activators. As per specific steps, insights and knowledge were validated with local and regional stakeholders during workshops jointly organised as part of other Work Packages. Visualisations of the current policy issues, inter-stakeholder interactions and power/interest matrix was developed by AEIDL based on the inputs of the Pilot Regions. Please note that inputs are based on perception of stakeholders.

Additionally, AEIDL collected further data on the specific indicators and data related to the country’s situation, their CAP and Cohesion Policy programmes for each Pilot Region/country. The following sources were consulted:

- Smart Rural 27 project country factsheets on Smart Villages planning
- EU CAP Network Fiches and European Commission CAP Strategic Plans fiches
- Cohesion Open Data Platform (planned finances for the 2021-2027 period)
- Rural Observatory, DESI and EIS/RIS platform indicators
- FAMENET Country factsheets on CLLD
- National websites from public authorities and Ministries

The section on Policy Options result from the discussions led at Pilot Region level. It identifies potential options for driving change through policy, which is provided in full in Annex 2.

⁵ Pazos-Vidal, S., & Lostrangio, C. (2024). Guidelines for policy audit / D6.1. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15182906>

⁶ Smart Rural 21 and 27 projects; Horizon projects GRANULAR, MOVING, SHERPA, FUTURAL.

⁷ Lostrangio, M. C. (2025). When smart villages meets rural diversity: Tailoring rural smartness to rural and remote areas. *European Urban and Regional Studies*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/09697764251379242>

⁸ Lostrangio, C., & Pazos-Vidal, S. (2025). Existing Policy and Governance frameworks for smart community-led innovation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15517550>

⁹ Lostrangio, C. (2025). The Non-Negligible Contribution of Rural Areas to Europe’s Innovation Ambitions. AEIDL Policy Brief. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17338023>

3. EU policies for smart rural areas

Over the last ten years, the concept of **smart rural areas** has earned momentum into EU-level policymaking and by rural territories and communities, up to becoming a hallmark for **territorial marketing** and **distinctiveness**¹⁰. Following the emergence of smart rural areas as a concept it is not surprising that this was coupled with a strong demand from communities themselves to own and put it in practice.¹¹ Indeed, it reflects a broader pattern towards digitalisation of society that is most prevalent in cities. It has arisen in parallel to the new **OECD rural well-being framework** (2020). The OECD 2020 framework hints rural areas as places of opportunities, in net contradiction with the former vision looking at rural areas as handicapped or less-innovative places¹². It also calls – at the same time of other rural-driven policy demand¹³ - for a more **integrated and multi-sectoral approach** to rural development.

At EU level, this view was formally institutionalised in 2021, with the launch of the [EU's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas by 2040](#) by the European Commission (hereinafter also called 'Rural Vision'). The Rural Vision provides the strategic framework for rural revitalisation alongside four macro-areas: stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous rural areas. The EU's Rural Vision promotes an **integrated approach** to rural development through a **multi-sectoral** set of actions (the Rural Action Plan), and the creation of **new governance frameworks** pursuing at the same time the break of political silos across Directorates of the European Commission, as well as a brand-new governance framework for engaging with rural actors at multiple levels (the EU Rural Pact).

In relation to rural innovation, by 2024, the **EU's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas** i) canalised € 250 million of investments in over 60 Horizon Europe research and innovation projects to enhance rural innovation; ii) conceptualised the characteristics and drivers of rural innovation via the Start-up Village Forum; iii) Developed guidance for the emergence of Smart Villages via the Smart Rural 21/27 projects, iv) Organised several thematic events leveraging on LEADER, EU CAP Network, Rural Pact, Rural Revitalisation Platform^{14, 15}.

Certainly, a lesson learnt from the EU's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas is that policies for **smart rural areas** cannot be reduced to a single policy area or Department. This novel EU's Rural Vision from 2022 onwards attempts to create an umbrella, and functional governance

¹⁰ Kormann-Hainzl, G., Lovasz-Bukvova, H., & Hoelzl, M. (2022). Are smart villages just smaller smart cities? Call for a Region-Type-Specific approach to the smartification of communities. *Central and Eastern European eDem and eGov Days*, 341, 115–125. <https://doi.org/10.24989/ocg.v341.8>

¹¹ Lostrangio, C. (2024). Smart Rurality: Reconciling Convergence with Growth and Wellbeing at Local Level?. AEIDL Policy Brief. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14515457>

¹² Cervantes-Godoy, D. (2022), "Aligning agricultural and rural development policies in the context of structural change", *OECD Food, Agriculture and Fisheries Papers*, No. 187, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/1499398c-en>.

¹³ A few examples: Cork Declaration, Smart Mountains Declaration, Smart Islands Declaration.

¹⁴ European Commission (2024). The long-term vision for the EU's rural areas: key achievements and ways forward. COM/2024/450 final.

¹⁵ European Commission (2024). COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT Taking stock of the implementation of the EU rural action plan (2021-2023). SWD/2024/450 final.

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structures, to bring together a set of existing policies, policy instruments and mechanisms, to seek a more synergetic approach. Whereas this is clear in theory, it seems less transparent in practice, as policy development does not always follow a linear approach nor respond to the same interests and advocacy requests. This chapter fills this gap by outlining, on one end, what **EU policy concepts** are linked with the notion of smart rural areas, and on the other hand, what **existing policies and policy instruments** are framing support to smart rural areas.

3.1 EU concepts

At the EU level, smart rural areas have been associated with different **EU policy concepts** acting at multiple territorial scales (Table 1). The most relevant ones are the Living Labs (also known as Multi-Actor Platforms or Science-Society-Policy Interfaces), CLLD/LEADER approach, Smart Villages, Startup Villages and Smart Specialisation.

Table 1 EU Concepts and Definitions related to smart rural areas

Concept	Scale	Technical definition	Legal Framework	Link to smart rural areas
Living Labs	Project/ Pilot	'Open innovation ecosystems where research and innovation unfold in real-life environment rather than in isolated laboratories' (ENoLL)	Regulation (EU) 2021/2115	Communities are part of innovation ecosystem
Smart Villages	Village, Town	<i>Communities in rural areas that develop smart solutions to deal with challenges in their own local context' (Smart Rural 21's Guidebook, n.d.: 2). 'Rural areas and communities which build on their existing strengths and assets as well as on developing new opportunities' (FAO, 2017)</i>	N/A	Supports innovation and experimentation in a rural village
Startup Villages	Village, Town	'A place (or a network of small places) that embraces innovation and ambitious entrepreneurship as a way to unlock development potential and support wellbeing in rural areas.' (Goodwin-Hawkins <i>et al.</i> , 2023)	N/A	Fosters entrepreneurial innovation and skills
CLLD/ LEADER	Sub regional	An EU instrument to place-based and community-led local development grounded on seven ingredients (bottom-up approach, local principle, integrated and multi-sector strategy, networking, innovation, cooperation).	Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 Art 3, Regulation (EU) 2021/106, Art. 31-34	Target local development and innovation through Local Development Strategies
Smart Specialisation	Regional National	Place-based innovation policy concept aimed to support regional prioritisation in innovative sectors, fields or technologies through the entrepreneurial discovery process', a bottom-up approach to reveal what a region does best in terms of its	Regulation (EU) 2021/1058	Sets up a strategy for industrial specialisation and matching business

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	scientific & technological endowments (Morrison & Pattinson, 2020)	needs with R&I strengths
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Source: Own elaboration.

The comparison of these concepts also allows us to reflect on how these concepts might be further refined in the future as to avoid overlapping, or demand for stronger regulatory uptake, e.g. through the development of specific legislative definitions in EU policy or legislative frameworks. It is worth noting that theory is different from reality. In other terms, while all these concepts potentially relate or offer potential for the notion of smart rural areas to develop, this has not always been experienced in real settings. For instance, many CLLD/LEADER programmes do not focus on innovation despite this being of the key drivers for local development according to the existing EU policy paradigms (Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas, LTVRA).

3.2 EU policies and instruments

Our analysis shows that **six policy frameworks particularly focus on specific programmes for community-led rural innovation** over the current programming period (Table 2). These are the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP); Cohesion Policy; European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF); the EU's Research and Innovation Programme; Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas; and the New European Bauhaus (the facto funded under Horizon Europe, as well as the Cohesion Policy and LIFE programme).

Table 2 Key EU policies, strategies and instruments for smart rural communities (2021-2027)

Policy name	Policy Instrument	Aims to
Common Agricultural Policy	LEADER programme (<i>since 1991</i>)	Engage local actors in the design and delivery of strategies for the development of rural areas
	Smart Villages (<i>since 2023</i>)	Foster community-driven innovation, digitalisation, connectivity, services in villages
	AKIS and EIP-AGRI (<i>since 2012</i>)	Modernise agriculture and rural areas by promoting cross-actor knowledge exchange and innovation
Cohesion Policy	CLLD programme (<i>since 2014</i>)	Involve local actors in delivering bottom-up development strategies in cities, rural, coastal, fisheries
	Smart Villages (<i>since 2021</i>)	As above
	Integrated Territorial Instruments (<i>since 2014</i>)	Deliver integrated territorial development (combining different funds, sectors) under cohesion policy
	Smart Specialisation Strategies	A place-based innovation policy allowing regions to identify their strengths and focus on growth/innovation accordingly.
EMFAF	CLLD (<i>since 2007</i>)	Community-led local development approach applied to fisheries and coastal, marine and river areas.
EU's research & innovation programme	'AKIS' in General calls and Partnerships (<i>since 2014</i>); Horizon Missions (<i>since 2021</i>)	The EU's programme for research and innovation. Incorporation of community-led innovation (Living Labs and similar) is supported under several calls.

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EU Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas	Rural Pact (<i>since 2021</i>)	Provide a multi-level framework to engage stakeholders for rural development
	Rural Action Plan	Identify and implement actions to achieve the Vision's goals. These include support to community-led innovation
	Startup Villages (<i>since 2021</i>)	Promote startup-driven innovation in rural areas
New EU Bauhaus	(<i>since 2021</i>)	Revitalise neighbourhoods through design for sustainability, inclusion, and cross-disciplinary actions.

Source: Own elaboration.

Under the above-mentioned policy frameworks, we can identify different policy instruments, in some cases repeated across several policy frameworks. First and foremost, the **LEADER/CLLD programme**, which is the main instrument targeting community-led innovation in Europe. Launched in 1991, the LEADER programme began as an experimental initiative seeking to support bottom-up local development in rural areas. Since 2014, the LEADER approach has been expanded to the other EU funds beyond the CAP (Cohesion Policy and EMFAF), where is referred to as CLLD¹⁶. CLLD has only some minor differences if compared to the LEADER programme, perhaps the main one is that it is not an exclusive of rural areas but in 2021-2027 it was widely promoted for urban areas too (with an 8% mandatory earmarking for Member States in their Cohesion Policy Operational Programmes)¹⁷.

The **Smart Villages instrument**, whose aim is to support community-led innovation in rural areas. This instrument was piloted at European level since 2017, and it was formally allowed to receive financial support in the CAP starting from 2023¹⁸. The Smart Villages were piloted across several EU countries and accompanied by technical research while being supported by the 2021-2027 period, especially thanks to the work done by the Smart Rural 21 and Smart Rural 27 projects both financed by the EU.

A third instrument is the EU's **Agricultural and Knowledge Innovation Systems (AKIS)** instrument and its **EIP-AGRI Operational Groups**¹⁹. Formally launched in 2014, this instrument was designed to increase innovation and knowledge co-production between scientific and practice actors in agricultural and rural development. Built around interaction of actors coming from science as well as practice, it has been financed both under CAP (as EIP-Operational Groups) and the EU's research and innovation programme (also known as Living Labs, Multi-Actor Platforms, Science-Society-Policy Interfaces).

The Cohesion Policy allows Managing Authorities to target rural innovation through two other instruments beyond CLLD and Smart Villages. One of these are **Smart Specialisation Strategies**, which provides a strategic approach to regional innovation beyond the rural

¹⁶ FAMENET (2025). [Working paper on CLLD evaluation](#).

¹⁷ ELARD. [About LEADER and CLLD](#).

¹⁸ Lostrangio, C. (2024). Smart Rurality: Reconciling Convergence with Growth and Wellbeing at Local Level?. AEIDL Policy Brief. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14515457>

¹⁹ European Commission (2019). Preparing for Future AKIS in Europe. Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR) 4th Report of the Strategic Working Group on Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS)

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dimension and community-led innovation. Smart Specialisation Strategies are an ex-ante condition to receive Cohesion Policy funds. However, these strategies do not purposely target to community-led rural innovation. This is an important gap towards the design and implementation of place-based innovation strategies. The other instrument, **Integrated Territorial Instruments** (ITIs), was introduced in 2014 to bundle resources from different funds or priority areas of the Cohesion Policy Operational Programmes for financing an integrated strategy linked to a certain territory or functional area. ITIs can be used to pool resources for rural areas, but findings show that impacts in these areas should be more closely assessed²⁰. However, some studies show that ITIs have mostly been used in urban settings over the 2014-20 period^{21,22}.

Of all instruments mentioned above, it is worth noting that the **LEADER programme** is the only long-standing instrument, followed by the **multi-actor approach** applied both via the AKIS instrument in the CAP and EU's Research and Innovation programme. Most other policies and policy instruments are relatively younger, with less than 10 years existence, hence still open to rough evolution and future negotiations.

Please note that the table above includes other policies or policy instruments offering support – financial, technical, networking – to community-led rural innovation. However, some of these instruments have not yet been fully developed (e.g. Startup Village) or they are not fully enshrined into legislative text (e.g. New EU Bauhaus, Rural Pact, Rural Action) which makes their continuation linked to the evolution of political priorities.

Annex 1 of this document provides a full list of relevant policies alongside the SMART ERA six policy dimensions for smart rural communities. Finally, other analyses show how community-led rural innovation is framed in other sectoral strategies and policy documents²³, and/or how other sectoral policies provide the enabling conditions for rural areas to support community-led innovation²⁴.

3.3 EU policies implementation

The section above presents the main policies and instruments currently available for community-led rural innovation. However, the existence of these policies does not mean they have been up taken by Member States, Managing Authorities, or other implementing actors. The question we raise in this section is: How many of the measures identified in section 3.2 are relevant and do reach these territories?

As said above, the LEADER programme is the most lasting and well-defined programme for community-led rural innovation. Clearance on LEADER from the EU legislative texts, as well

²⁰ European Parliament (2019). Integrated Territorial Investments as an effective tool of the Cohesion Policy. In-Depth Analysis.

²¹ Ferry, M. (2019). Integrated Territorial Investments as an Effective Tool of the Cohesion Policy. European Parliament.

²² CEMR (2022). ITI and CLLD. The use of integrated territorial tools in cohesion policy.

²³ Lostrangio, C., & Pazos-Vidal, S. (2025). Existing Policy and Governance frameworks for smart community-led innovation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15517550>

²⁴ Lostrangio, C. (2024). Smart Rurality: Reconciling Convergence with Growth and Wellbeing at Local Level?. AEIDL Policy Brief. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14515457>

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as targeting and monitoring of data allows it to simply follow its progress and state of the art. Today, the LEADER programme covers **65% of the EU-27 rural areas** and it received **7.7% of the EU CAP Pillar II (EAFRD)** in the 2023-2027 CAP, which is beyond the 5% minimum earmarking defined in the CAP regulation²⁵. It is also a significant increase in size if we consider that the first edition of the LEADER programme in the early 90s counted on approximately 271 Local Action Groups, whereas today it finances 2,678 LAGs²⁶.

Compared to the 2014-20 period, the EU Member States' budget allocated to the LEADER programme has slightly increased in absolute terms (Figure 1), with some significant differences across countries. In the 2023-27 period, Germany is the country with the highest percentage of EAFRD dedicated to leader (approximately 15% of the total), followed by Estonia and Spain.

Figure 1 LEADER allocation as % of EAFRD (CAP Plans 2023-27 and Rural Development Plans 2014-22). Source: European Commission (2024)²⁷.

If we look at the **CLLD** – as said the respective of LEADER in Cohesion Policy – the latest data show that Member States planned for **€ 750 million for CLLD, with only half of these going to rural areas**²⁸. This means that the funds provided by the Cohesion Policy to CLLD are significantly lower than the ones channelled from CAP to LEADER. This gap is even more relevant if we consider that the budget for rural development (beyond agriculture) is twice as big in the Cohesion Policy than the CAP²⁹.

²⁵ EU CAP Network. [LEADER facts and figures: New LAGs for 2023-2027 | EU CAP Network](#). June 13, 2023.

²⁶ *Ibid.*

²⁷ Lisztwan, I. (2023). First look at LEADER intervention in CAP Plans 2023-27. [Presentation](#). 2023-04.

²⁸ European Commission (2023). Cohesion 2021-2027: forging an ever stronger Union Report on the outcome of 2021-2027 cohesion policy programming.

²⁹ European Commission (2023). Taking stock of how CAP strategic plans contribute to the objectives of the long-term vision for the EU's rural areas.

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Over the 2021-2027 period, the STRAT-Board platform records 500 CLLD strategies and 385 Integrated Territorial Investments across Member States via the Cohesion Policy (out of a sample of 1426 collected strategies) (Figure 2)³⁰. Of these available data, we can observe **CLLD is comparatively used more in rural areas than Integrated Territorial Investments** via the Cohesion Policy. Notably, of the **total reported CLLD strategies**, 376 (75.2%) are explicitly assigned to rural areas, 13 (2.6%) to mountain territories, and 4 (0.8%) to islands and coastal areas. On the reverse, only 13 Integrated Territorial Investments are designed for rural areas (3.4%), 7 (1.8%) for mountain areas, and 8 (2%) for islands and other coastal territories, whereas the remaining amount is shared between different types of urban areas and functional urban areas (see also Figure 3).

Figure 2 Map of Cohesion Policy measures across Member States (per territorial focus) [2021-2027 period]. Source: EU Strat-Board. Accessed on 20/10/2025.

³⁰ Please note that at the time this report is drafted, data on STRAT-Board does cover only 10 EU Member States and are not complete.

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Figure 3 Distribution of Cohesion Policy strategies targeting rural, mountainous, sparsely population, islands and coastal areas [2021-2027]. Source: EU Strat-Board. Accessed on 20/10/2025.

Additionally, CLLD is also financed via the EMFAF since 2007. Approximately € 612 million (10%) of the total EMFAF budget was committed to CLLD in the 2021-2027 period, covering approximate 350 Fisheries Local Action Groups³¹. Figure 4 illustrates the distribution of CLLD-funded Local Action Groups in coastal and other water-related areas in Europe. Despite no actual evaluation of CLLD implementation exist, available data shows that 'CLLD was by far the most effective EMFAF measure for job creation'³² with more than 10,000 jobs being maintained thanks to Fisheries Local Action Groups (FLAGs), 1,020 businesses were created through CLLD support, and approximately 1,520 local innovations were enabled.

³¹ FAMENET (2024). What does CLLD bring to coastal and fisheries communities around Europe?

³² *Ibid.* Pag. 3.

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Figure 4 Distribution of Fisheries Local Action Groups in Europe [2021-2027 period]. Source: FAMENET.

With respect to **Smart Villages**, data shows that, by 2025, only 5 Member States designed dedicated measures to support Smart Villages (Austria, Finland, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania) in their CAP Strategic Plans, whereas 18 Member States allow financial support to Smart villages via the LEADER specific interventions³³. At EU level, Smart villages are entitled to receive financial support under the Cohesion Policy, under the ERDF and Cohesion Fund, but there are no studies at present stocktaking of this instrument uptake at EU level.

In terms of **Smart Specialisation Strategies**, there are no institutional studies mapping their contribution to innovation in rural areas. However, some scholars claim that very few contributed to the ‘smartification’ of rural areas³⁴.

³³ Makrandreou, M. EU Commission - DG AGRI. 3rd meeting of the Subgroup on LEADER and Territorial Dimension. 5-6 March 2025.

³⁴ Sörvik, J., Teräs, J., Dubois, A., & Pertoldi, M. (2018). Smart Specialisation in sparsely populated areas: challenges, opportunities and new openings. *Regional Studies*, 53(7), 1070–1080. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2018.1530752>; Torre A, Corsi S, Steiner M, Wallet F, Westlund H (2022) *Smart Development for Rural Areas*. Abingdon: Routledge, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429354670>.

4. Policies in SMART ERA Pilot Regions

4.1. Countries covered by SMART ERA

The SMART ERA Pilot Regions are situated in **6 European countries**, of which there are 5 EU Member States and 1 non-EU member state. All these countries are characterised by a **relevant presence of rural surface and rural population** (Table 3). Of the SMART ERA Pilot Regions, Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) is the first country both in terms of rural population and rural surface. In addition to BiH, three other European countries (Slovenia, Bulgaria and Finland) are also above the EU-average in terms of rural population. Three countries (Spain, Finland and Slovenia) exceed the EU-average in terms of rural land surface.³⁵

Rural areas covered by SMART ERA Pilot Regions are also extremely different from one another. A remarkable difference elucidating the heterogeneity of rural territory across analysed countries (and in Europe) is the proportion between the share of **rural areas close to cities and remote rural areas**. Whereas this share is partially equally divided in countries such as Bulgaria, Spain and Italy, the situation is very different in Slovenia and Finland (Table 3). In Slovenia, about half of the national surface is composed by rural areas close to urban centres, and only a fourth of the national surface are remote rural areas. This relation is inverted in Finland, where more than 70% of the country surface is covered by remote rural areas, and only 6% are rural areas close to cities.

Additionally, as reported by indicators of the Regional Innovation Scoreboard (RIS), SMART ERA Pilot Regions in Finland, Italy and Slovenia are located into NUTS2 regions with a comparatively **higher level of innovation**, compared to the Spanish Pilot Area ('moderate level') and the Bulgarian and BiH Pilot Regions (Table 3). Additionally, other indicators related to employment, digitalisation and innovation confirm structural differences across SMART ERA Pilot Regions, as detailed in the table below.

Table 3 Selected context and performance indicators in countries covered by SMART ERA

	BiH	BG	ES	FI	IT	SI	EU-27
Rural population	49.00%	22.40%	13.32%	26.42%	17.01%	44.67%	25.57%
<i>Rural areas, close to a city</i>	-	13.14%	9.19%	8.52%	12.16%	36.28%	18.14%
<i>Rural areas, remote</i>	-	9.26%	4.13%	17.90%	4.85%	8.39%	7.43%
Rural land surface	97.50%	56.58%	73.23%	77.68%	60.98%	75.31%	75.73%
<i>Rural areas, close to a city</i>	-	30.55%	33.48%	6.31%	32.01%	51.53%	34.21%
<i>Rural areas, remote</i>	-	26.03%	39.75%	71.37%	28.97%	23.78%	41.52%
Employment sector in predominantly rural regions							
Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing							

³⁵ World Bank. (2024). *World Development Indicators*. Share of rural population Retrieved from <https://data.worldbank.org>
Eurostat. (2022). *Land use statistics – Agricultural and forest land in the EU*. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
World Bank. (2021). *World Development Indicators. Agricultural land (sq. km)* Retrieved from <https://data.worldbank.org>

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<i>% of employed in the sector</i>	18%	6%	4%	3.61%	3.9%	4.03%	4.1%
<i>absolute (thousands people)</i>	-	104.9	65.01	56	186.8	52.7	8460
Industry, excluding Construction							
<i>% of employed in the sector</i>	-	12.58%	2.72%	43.29%	9.54%	63.58%	-
<i>absolute (thousands people)</i>	-	83.4	62.7	168.2	415	157.2	-
Construction							
<i>% of employed in the sector</i>	-	8.86%	3.47%	38.33%	11.41%	56.55%	-
<i>absolute (thousands people)</i>	-	17.2	48.5	78.5	203.6	49.2	-
Wholesale, retail, transport, accommodation & food services, ICT							
<i>% of employed in the sector</i>	-	7.86%	2.90%	30.72%	9.17%	44.04%	-
<i>absolute (thousands people)</i>	-	80.2	194.4	202.3	51.76	118.7	-
Financial and Business Services							
<i>% of employed in the sector</i>	-	4.21%	1.72%	25.13%	7.98%	37.28%	-
<i>% of employed in the sector</i>	-	14.8	56.4	115.7	337.8	63	-
Non-Market Services							
<i>% of employed in the sector</i>	-	10.13%	3.18%	39.37%	9.98%	48.07%	-
<i>absolute (thousands people)</i>	-	74.5	212.5	384.6	747.3	122.3	-
Other Structural Indicators							
<i>Degree of urbanisation (%)</i>	-	72	86.7	74.2	84.1	56.4	76.1
<i>Population density</i>	63	58.6	96.2	18.4	198.1	105.3	109.3
<i>GDP per capita (PPS)</i>	35	66	92	103	98	91	100
Infrastructure and accessibility							
Broadband speed (mobile networks)(Mb/s)							
<i>in Rural areas</i>	-	105.82	56.04	112.02	78.37	81.15	81.1
<i>Gap from cities</i>	-	80.17	78.57	67.68	30.23	60.89	64.53
Broadband speed (fixed networks) (Mb/s)							
<i>in Rural areas</i>	-	55.96	185.08	147.65	84.79	125.52	144.61
<i>Gap from cities</i>	-	57	60.98	37.55	97.2	64.2	61.07
Digital Economy and Society Index (NUTS1)							
<i>Internet use</i>	-	81.92%	94.98%	95.27%	88.06%	89.65%	91.67%
<i>At least basic digital skills</i>	38%	35.52%	66.18%	81.99%	45.75%	46.70%	55.56%
<i>Above basic digital skills</i>	-	7.73%	38.65%	53.63%	22.21%	18.88%	27.32%
<i>Digital public services for citizens</i>	-	67.98	88.75	96.32	83.75	78.58	82.32
<i>Digital public services for businesses</i>	-	94.04	85.11	98.75	80.93	85.00	86.23
European Innovation Scoreboard (NUTS1)							
<i>Innovation Index</i>	28.9	51.6	104.3	141.1	104.7	106.6	112.6
<i>Innovator Level</i>	Emerging	Emerging	Moderate	Leader	Moderate	Moderate	-
Regional Innovation Scoreboard (NUTS2)							
<i>Innovation Index</i>	East Herzegovina	Severntsentralen	Iles Balears	North & East Finland	Autonomous Province of Trento	Western Slovenia	-
<i>Innovation Index</i>	-	44.9	81.8	128.5	119.5	121.9	112.6
<i>Innovation Level</i>	-	Emerging	Moderate	Strong	Strong	Strong	-

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<i>Broadband penetration</i>	-	69.9	128.3	112.1	106.1	120.3	-
<i>R&D expenditure in the public sector</i>	-	0	37	134.2	115.1	116.4	-
<i>R&D expenditure in the business sector</i>	-	43.5	34.9	109.7	64.7	107.2	-
<i>SMEs introducing product innovations</i>	-	43	33	103.2	140.4	156.1	-
<i>SMEs introducing business process innovations</i>	-	19.1	30.9	101.1	155.6	104.6	-

Source: Own Elaboration, based on Rural Observatory, DESI and EIS and RIS indicators.

The heterogeneity of rural areas across SMART ERA covered countries is reflected by the diversity of definitions being used to capture 'rural areas' at national level, through the CAP Strategic Plans (Table 4).

Table 4 Comparison of 'rural areas' definition as per national CAP Strategic Plans (2023-27)

'Rural' Definition in the 2023-2027 CAP Strategic Plans	
Bosnia and Herzegovina	n/a
Bulgaria	Municipalities in which there is no settlement with a population of more than 15,000 people.
Spain	No national legislation on identification of rural areas applicable to EAFRD, but general definition of rural areas or specific definitions in some interventions have been identified by regional and supra-autonomous authorities.
Finland	The definition of the eligible rural area of mainland Finland in business and development projects is based on the use of spatial datasets covering the area. The Finnish Environment Institute maintains a municipal structure monitoring system, which has a time series in the 250x250 m grid. Grid-based datasets enable a classification independent of administrative borders, which may be accompanied by other datasets independent of administrative boundaries.
Italy	It applies the same definition of rural development policy 2014-2022. This definition classifies Italian municipalities into four areas, namely: urban and peri-urban areas; rural areas with intensive agriculture; intermediate rural areas; and rural areas with development problems.
Slovenia	Rural areas for the implementation of the LEADER intervention are considered all settlements with less than 10 000 inhabitants.

Source: EU CAP Factsheets: Key Facts and Figures. July 2024.

Smart rural development policies aim at improving rural wellbeing, delivery of services and fostering the ability of rural residents to stay and live in rural areas. However, the **way to achieve this goal might diverge** according to rural specificities in line with the principle of **place-based development**. The following subchapters provide a detailed description of selected countries and Pilot Regions, their need and specificities, and how policy can leverage them to drive smart rural development.

4.2. Bulgaria

Bulgaria is a **unitary country** organised along three levels of governance, going from central government to districts and municipalities. Since 2006, the country has been undergoing a

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decentralisation process, aimed at the transfer of competences and resources to lower-level authorities³⁶, leading to the update of the [Decentralisation Strategy \(2016-25\)](#).

In Bulgaria, rural areas account for somewhat more than **half of the national land surface**, and rural residents equal approximately **22% of the total population**. Both values are slightly below the EU-27 average (Rural Observatory, 2021). According to the latest national CAP definition, rural areas include municipalities in which there is no settlement with a population of more than 15,000 people³⁷. Following this criteria, 215 municipalities out of 265 municipalities are classified as rural areas. It is interesting to note that this new definition, introduced with the 2023-2027 National CAP Strategic Plan, cut by half the population threshold to identify rural areas (formally established at 30,000 people).

Compared to other EU-27 countries, Bulgarian rural areas are still highly dependent on **agriculture**, and they lag in several indicators related to **socio-economic development**³⁸. **Demographic changes, high risk of poverty and limited access to essential services** are critical issues at the national level^{39, 40}. In the 2007-2022 period, rural depopulation has been twice as fast as the average population loss in entire country⁴¹.

Furthermore, the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is approximately a third lower than the EU-27 average, with no major differences between rural and non-rural areas (Table 3). The country's indicators on broadband speed (fixed networks), digital skills and access to digital services for citizens is lower than the EU-27 countries. **Agriculture, forestry and fishing** are the main sectors in terms of the people employed in predominantly rural regions, and the total share of rural workers equals one fifth of all workers in the sector (Table 3).

Overall, **territorial disparities** in Bulgaria have been increasing since 1960s due to concentration of public investments in urban areas, EU integration, and multiple crises (financial, sanitary etc), and efforts made towards decentralization have not yet achieved the intended impacts⁴².

National policies

The table below lists the main policies and strategies accompanying smart rural development in Bulgaria. Since 2007, date of entry in the EU, Bulgaria implements rural

³⁶ Stamenkov, I. (2022): Country Profile of Bulgaria. Hannover. = ARL Country Profiles. <https://www.arl-international.com/knowledge/country-profiles/bulgaria/rev/3729>. Last access: 06/10/2025.

³⁷ EU CAP Network. CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027: Facts and Figures. Bulgaria country factsheet. July 2024.

³⁸ Hristov, K., Beluhova-Uzunova, R., Ivanova, B., Shishkova, M., Todorov, G. (2025). The European Union Long Term Vision For Rural Areas - Prospects For Bulgaria. 2025. Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering In Agriculture And Rural Development Vol. 25, Issue 2, 2025 Print Issn 2284-7995, E-Issn 2285-3952.

³⁹ Smart Rural 27 project (2024). [Taskforce Action Plan. Bulgaria](#). Last updated: 02/02/2024.

⁴⁰ Petrov K (2020). The Regional Variations And Peculiarities In The Structuring And Development Of Rural Areas In Bulgaria. Scientific Papers. Series "Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and rural development", Vol. 20 ISSUE 4, PRINT ISSN 2284-7995, 381-388.

⁴¹ Romanchuk, Liudmyla & Abramova, Iryna & Moroz, Yuliia & Poplavskiy, Pavlo & Svitlyshyn, Ihor, 2024. "Funding for sustainable development of rural communities: European experience," Agricultural and Resource Economics: International Scientific E-Journal, Agricultural and Resource Economics: International Scientific E-Journal, vol. 10(4), December.

⁴² OECD (2021), Decentralisation and Regionalisation in Bulgaria: Towards Balanced Regional Development, OECD Multi-level Governance Studies, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/b5ab8109-en>.

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development policies through the programmes CAP and Cohesion Policy. In addition to this, the country defined a few national plans for countering **depopulation**, increasing accessibility to **essential services** (in particular **healthcare** and **transport**), and boosting **digital transformation**. The National Development Programme of Bulgaria 2030 identifies ‘**quality of life in rural areas**’ and ‘**local development**’ (including the community-led development through the CLLD programme) as priority areas. However, Yarkova & Mutafov (2017)⁴³ report that national policies are insufficient to accompany the development of rural areas in Bulgaria. As shown in the table below, the role of rural areas in other strategies and policy documents is not always addressed.

Table 5 Relevant policies and strategies for smart rural areas (Bulgaria)

Policy name	Aims to
<u>National Development Programme Bulgaria 2030</u>	Outline the vision for sustainable development. It includes measures to increase quality of life and service accessibility in rural areas, counter demographic trends, digitalisation in agriculture and rural areas, and community-led initiatives
<u>National Demographic Strategy of Bulgaria (2012–30)</u>	Mitigating population demographic by improving birth rates, reducing mortality, limiting emigration, supporting more equal territorial distribution and quality of life
<u>National Health Strategy 2030</u>	Improve healthcare accessibility, but it does not specifically address telemedicine use in rural areas
<u>Strategy for Digital Transformation of Bulgaria (2023-30)</u>	Create conditions to enable innovation, growth and a digital economy. Agricultural digitalization is targeted but not rural digitalisation in broader term
<u>National Transport Strategy (2021-30)</u>	Recognise rural connectivity as a challenge but does not mandate specific solutions for small villages
<u>National Broadband Infrastructure Plan for Next Generation Access (2020-30)</u>	Prioritise investments in 5G deployment, high-speed internet access, and investment-friendly policies. Development of rural and peripheral areas is one of the strategic objectives
<u>National Concept for Spatial Development (2013-25)</u>	Define the medium-term spatial framework for all development investments in Bulgaria according to the principle of polycentric development
<u>Law on Regional Development</u>	Define the long-term objectives of regional development
<u>Law on Amendment and Supplement to the Regional Development Act</u>	Reduce the number of strategic documents and administrative burden to simplify the process for monitoring, control and evaluation of regional development policy
<u>Local Government and local administration Act</u>	Define responsibilities of municipal authorities, including in areas with exclusive competences (housing, community-amenities, state-shared duties on education and social care)

Source: Own elaboration.

In its **CAP Strategic Plan (2023-27)**, Bulgaria targets innovation via a number of measures and specific indicators throughout AKIS, EIP Operational Groups, digitalisation in agriculture and investments measures (Table 6). Among these, Bulgaria allocates **8% of its EAFRD funds** to the LEADER programme (above the mandatory threshold of 5% EAFRD funds

⁴³ Yarkova, Y., & Mutafov, E. (2017). Rural Areas In Bulgaria – Investigation on some factors for development. *Eastern European Countryside*, 23(1), 51–70. <https://doi.org/10.1515/Eec-2017-0003>

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allocation). This budget is intended to cover 80% of the rural population and finance 80 local development strategies and 3 preparatory actions/projects.

Table 6 Selected indicators from the CAP Strategic Plan Bulgaria (2023-27)

Selected Indicators	Bulgaria
<i>R.1 Enhancing performance through knowledge and innovation</i>	210,200
<i>R.3 Digitalisation agriculture</i>	12.84%
<i>R.39 developing the rural economy</i>	802
<i>O.1 No of EIP operational group projects</i>	341
<i>O.23 No of supported off-farm non-productive investment operations or units</i>	1,802
<i>O.24 No of supported off-farm productive investment operations or units</i>	1,252
<i>O.27 No of rural businesses receiving support for startup</i>	-
LEADER indicators	
<i>Population coverage</i>	2,812,687
<i>Population coverage (%) - R38</i>	80%
<i>Local Development Strategies</i>	80
<i>Preparatory Actions/Projects</i>	3
<i>Budget (€)</i>	€ 113,865,060
<i>Budget (% of EAFRD funds)</i>	8%

Source: Own Elaboration. Adapted from EU CAP Network CAP Strategic Plans Factsheets (2024) and Catalogue of CAP Intervention Dashboard.

Bulgaria defines **Smart Villages** in its CAP Strategic Plan (2023-27) as an approach towards integrated territorial development and improved their economic, social and/or environmental conditions in rural areas. Nonetheless, the Strategic Plan does not design any dedicated interventions for supporting Smart Villages, nor a specific result indicator and budget. It is possible to foresee support for the '**creation of smart settlements** throughout the LEADER intervention (Table 7).

Table 7 Smart Villages in approved CAP Strategic Plans Bulgaria (2023-27)

Bulgaria	
Definition	Smart Villages is an approach to integrated territorial development based on a concept (a simplified version of a strategy or strategy) for its application and/or as separate, independent innovative, social, technological and/or digital solutions corresponding to the principles of this concept as a tool/s for the territorial development of rural areas intended to improve their economic, social and/or environmental conditions.
Dedicated interventions	n/a
Other Interventions	II.G.5 - Implementation of operations, including cooperation activities and their preparation, selected under the local development strategy (LEADER).
R40	n/a
Budget	n/a

Source: Own elaboration adapted from Smart Rural 27 (2024). Bulgarian factsheet.

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In Bulgaria, **Cohesion Policy** is defined through national-wide Operational Programmes. The table below reports the planned allocations to CLLD, ITIs and other territorial tools as across the planned Operational Programmes in areas which are non-urban (Table 8). It is possible to derive three main conclusions.

First, several Operational Programmes intend to finance Integrated Territorial Tools and other territorial tools and, to a lesser extent, CLLD in non-rural areas (3 Operational Programmes). **Second**, CLLD is planned to be financed both via ERDF and ESF+ funds, targeting specific objectives on research and innovation, circular economy, integration of marginalised communities such as the Roma community, access to job opportunities and adaptation of skills to the job market needs. **Third**, whereas actual planning of CLLD, ITIs or other territories tools to boost integrated territorial planning, **no one of these is earmarked to rural areas**, hence leaving unsecured its contribution on rural territories.

Table 8 Contribution to rural development from the national Operational Programmes of Cohesion Policy - Bulgaria (2021-2027)

Operational Programme Name	Specific Objective(s) Targeted:	Total contribution (million €)	Territorial code
Competitiveness and Innovation OP (ERDF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to CLLD (non-urban)</i>	RSO1.1; RSO2.6	€ 28.60	16 (Other territories)
<i>Of which dedicated to ITI</i>	RSO2.6; RSO1.3	€ 119.04	8 (Other territories)
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	RSO1.1; RSO1.2; RSO1.3 ; RSO2.1; RSO2.6	€ 1,306.25	33 (No territorial targeting)
Development of Regions (JTF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to ITI</i>	RSP5.2	€ 1,282.50	8 (Other territories)
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	JSO8.1	€ 1,407.16	32 (Other territories)
Education Programme (ESF+)			
<i>Of which dedicated to CLLD (non-urban)</i>	ESO4.10	€ 17.99	16 (Other territories)
<i>Of which dedicated to ITI</i>	ESO4.5; ESO4.7; ESO4.10	€ 91.06	8 (Other territories)
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	ESO4.5; ESO4.6; ESO4.7; ESO4.10	€ 809.30	33 (No territorial targeting)
Environment (ERDF, CF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to ITI</i>	RSO2.4; RSO2.7	€ 96.74	8 (Other territories)
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	RSO2.4; RSO2.5; RSO2.6; RSP2.7	€ 1,684.90	33 (No territorial targeting)
Human Resources Development Programme (ESF+)			

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<i>Of which dedicated to CLLD (non-urban)</i>	ESO4.1; ESO4.4; ESO4.10	€ 37.98	16 (Other territories)
<i>Of which dedicated to ITI</i>	ESO4.1; ESO4.4; ESO4.7; ESO4.8; ESO4.10; ESO4.11	€ 30.00	8 (Other territories)
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	ESO4.1; ESO4.2; ESO4.3; ESO4.4; ESO4.7; ESO4.8; ESO4.10; ESO4.11	€ 1,796.23	33 (No territorial targeting)
Research, Innovation and Digitalisation (ERDF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to ITI</i>	RSO1.1	€ 105.31	8 (Other territories)
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	RSO1.1; RSO1.2; RSO1.4	€ 962.27	33 (No territorial targeting)
Transport Connectivity (ERDF, CF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	RSO3.1	€ 1,817.60	33 (No territorial targeting)
Total Budget for CLLD (non-urban areas)			€ 84.57
<i>Of which CLLD for rural areas</i>			€ -
Total Budget for ITIs and other territorial instruments			€ 11,508.36
<i>Of which to rural areas</i>			€ -

Source: Own elaboration, adapted from Cohesion Open Data (2025).

Over the 2021-2027 period, Bulgaria decided to support 15 Local Action Groups of its **EMFAF budget** for community-led fisheries and aquaculture, which is an increase compared to 9 Local Action Groups in the previous programming period⁴⁴.

SMART ERA Pilot Region: Devetaki Plateau

The SMART ERA Pilot Region in Bulgaria covers the area of the **Devetaki Plateau**. The Devetaki Plateau is situated in the middle of Northern Bulgaria, and it includes **nine villages** across **three municipalities** (Lovech, Sevlievo, Letnitsa). This territory is included in the Natura 2000 National Ecological Network, and it has outstanding cultural and historical heritage spanning across local folklore, local cuisine and rituals, vernacular architecture.

Three **critical issues** affect the Devetaki Plateau: **demographic decline** (already today 45% of the population is over 65-year-old), **limited access to healthcare** and **poor connectivity infrastructures** (both digital and physical) (Figure 5).

These issues produce **economic stagnation** and contribute to exacerbating the demographic decline of the region. The negative loop of rural depopulation and limited investments started more than 30 years ago, but it has been severely affected by economic and other crises, such as the healthcare crises in 2020s with the COVID-19 pandemic. Whereas the entire Pilot region is affected by the three issues above-mentioned, such challenges are more severe in specific municipalities.

⁴⁴ European Commission. Programme Summary European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund - Programme for Bulgaria. CCI: 2021BG14MFPR001. [EMFAF programmes 2021 - 2027 - Oceans and fisheries - European Commission](#)

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Actors suffering the most from these issues are vulnerable groups – such as **elderly and other vulnerable categories** – as well as **youth and families**, who have limited opportunities in the rural areas of the Devetaki Plateau compared to other territories in the country. Similarly, **small businesses and entrepreneurs** are affected in their capacity of providing cost-effective solutions and access to essential services for their businesses, such as digital infrastructure and skilled talents. Finally, local authorities are resource-constrained and often unable to address crucial challenges with a shrinking population, leading to smaller financial resources.

WHAT and WHY

Figure 5 The vicious cycle in the Pilot Devetaki Plateau. Source: Own elaboration.

Over the last 10 years, the Devetaki Plateau began its transition from agriculture-oriented economy to become a tourism destination. Small rural businesses have started to offer accommodation, food, and other services for tourists, and the Devetaki Plateau Association and the three municipalities have invested resources in small tourist infrastructure and territorial marketing.

Relevant policies at Pilot level

Municipal duties and resources (to address these duties) are mandated respectively by the Bulgarian Local Government and local administration Act, and the Municipal Budgets Act. Overall, Bulgarian municipal authorities are **highly dependent on budget transfers** from the central government and the share of municipal budgets as part of the national public revenue is well below EU average (16% in Bulgaria vs. 25% EU average, 2016)⁴⁵.

⁴⁵ CoR – Divisions of Power. Bulgaria Introduction

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In 2016, the Public Finance Act was amended to include a new chapter VIII in which Municipalities with financial difficulties provided incentives to increase existing local taxes and created the basis for increased political dependence through non-interest-bearing loans' and latest reforms were introduced to ensure that a minimum level of local services is provided to the population in every municipality⁴⁶.

In the Devetaki Plateau, the main policies for smart rural transition are presented in Table 9. Above all are is the **Integrated Development Plan for Sevlievo Municipality**, which provides a comprehensive plan to guiding the region's development in a sustainable, inclusive, and strategic manner, with specific attention to tourism and waste management. The Integrated Development Plan is a **new instrument for territorial development** in Bulgaria, born from the integration of the Municipal Development Plans and the Integrated Plans for Urban Regeneration and Development⁴⁷.

In addition, the **Integrated Territorial Strategy for the North Central Region** defines the NUTS2 spatial development strategies in alignment with the National Concept for Spatial Development, encompassing the core urban centres, and territories with specific characteristics and functional areas.

Table 9 Relevant policies and strategies for smart rural areas in the Devetaki Plateau

Policy name	Aims to
Integrated Development Plan for Sevlievo Municipality	Prioritise sustainable development, equal opportunities, and social inclusion; and emphasise integrated territorial investments and partnerships with neighbouring municipalities.
Integrated Territorial Strategy for the North Central Region (NUTS2)	Defines the integrated territorial development priorities of the region
Municipal Master Plan of Sevlievo (until 2035)	Regulate traffic distribution and organization in Sevlievo

Source: Own elaboration.

Finally, the Devetaki Plateau host two **local action groups** (LAG), namely LAG Letnitsa - Lovech, and LAG Sevlievo. These LAGs have a focus on the development and improvement of the living environment in the villages. However, the new Program period has been delayed for almost 2 years now due to the political situation in Bulgaria, which hinders a lot of potential LAG-funded initiatives in the area.

Policy Gaps

Legislative and Strategic Gap: There is no structured national policy for rural development, leading to fragmented initiatives and weak institutional accountability. Other national

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

⁴⁷ Banaszczyk, A., Hinov, A., Kirchev, A., Masic, J., Petrov, Z., Wolszczak, G. An Analysis of the Possibilities to Implement Territorial Instruments : Program for Development of the Regions 2021 - 2027 (English). Washington, DC. : World Bank Group. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/857861617098152281>

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strategies lack tailored implementation for rural areas (e.g. Health plans overlook telemedicine; transport policies ignore rural micro-mobility and digital tools). Digital infrastructure plans remain urban-focused, with no fast-tracking for rural connectivity. Tourism lacks a smart or sustainable strategy, and municipalities aren't required to use data for planning.

Data Gap: Local authorities lack tools and capacity to collect and analyse data-especially in tourism, where visitor trends and impacts are not tracked. Without data, effective planning, marketing, and evaluation are limited across all sectors unassessed, making it difficult to adapt or refine strategies based on real outcomes.

Capacity Gap: Local governments lack trained staff and digital skills to implement smart rural solutions. Low digital literacy among residents and businesses limits uptake, while many small enterprises struggle to access rural development funding.

Funding and Investment Gap: Essential services like health, transport, culture, and education are underfunded, worsening social isolation and demographic decline. Poor infrastructure-roads, water systems-limits quality of life and deters tourism and investment.

Political stability Gap: six national elections in three years have delayed the implementation of EU funding programs and disrupted regional cooperation efforts.

Governance Gap: poor coordination between municipalities, preventing joint planning and shared investment in infrastructure or tourism development.

Digital Gap: Broadband expansion prioritises urban areas, with no incentives for rural rollout. Digital literacy programs are lacking, limiting innovation and tech adoption in rural communities.

Tourism Development Gap: no clear incentives for rural eco-tourism. Small rural businesses and tourism providers lack the capacity, knowledge and time to access available funding. The absence of environmental governance mechanisms, such as intelligent waste management systems or local sustainability plans, undermines efforts to protect the region's natural assets.

From Policy Opportunities to Policy Options

For the smart development of Devetaki Plateau, the SMART ERA Pilot Region has identified **two areas for policy development**, i.e. policy opportunity. One key opportunity lies in leveraging **telemedicine** to improve healthcare access across the region's remote villages. With the global advancement of digital health technologies, tailored telemedicine initiatives could be introduced, supported by EU and national funding programs aimed at digital transition. By training local medical professionals and raising public awareness about telehealth tools, municipalities and can pilot scalable models of rural healthcare delivery.

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Another major policy opportunity lies in sustainable territorial development, especially through **improved waste management systems** and **support for community-led tourism**. Both areas of development can contribute to preserve and strengthen the natural and social capital of the Pilot Region, hence contributing to revitalising socio-economic conditions. Digital tools and active community participation are seen as a leverage method to allow for data collection, monitoring and actual delivery, providing remote healthcare support, giving residents access to medical consultations without requiring travel to cities.

In line with these opportunities, the Devetaki Pilot Region formulated **four Policy Options** to revitalise rural communities in its territory (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Policy Options for the Devetaki Plateau Pilot Region.

The Devetaki Plateau Policy Options range from areas arisen from policy opportunities, namely in **rural telemedicine** and **community-driven transport**, to wider enabling Policy Options on **digital literacy** to and **smart eco-tourism and farming incentives**. Details on each Policy Option can be found in Annex 2.

4.3. Bosnia and Herzegovina

Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) is a **federal decentralised state** situated in the western part of the Balkan peninsula. The country **administrative structure** consists of two entities - the Federation of BiH and the Republic of Srpska (each covering approximately half of the country) and the Brčko District of BiH as a separate local government unit outside of the two entities for the remaining 1% of the country surface⁴⁸. Additionally, the country comprises **4 tiers of governance**, at the State, Entity, Canton and municipal levels. Such complex administrative and institutional compositions mirror the rich and multi-layered societal composition of the country, in terms of ethnicity, faith and sense of identity.

The country does not have legally prescribed criteria to identify rural areas⁴⁹, though a definition of urban settlements exists (Law 129/2009; 83/2014). Nevertheless, based on the

⁴⁸ Bijelić, B. (2024): Country Profile Of Bosnia & Herzegovina. Hannover. = ARL Country Profiles. <https://www.Arl-International.Com/Knowledge/Country-Profiles/Bosnia-Herzegovina/Rev/4067>.

⁴⁹ Ministry Of Foreign Trade And Economic Relations Of Bosnia And Herzegovina (2024). Strategic Plan For Rural Development of Bih (2023–2027).

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OECD criterion, rural areas count for **97.50% of the country's surface** and **49% of its population**⁵⁰.

Rural areas in BiH have quite some differences from the rest of EU⁵¹. First, the share of rural population is twice the EU-27 average. Second, large parts of rural areas are considerably remote and mountainous, experiencing serious obstacles in terms of connectivity and infrastructure development. Third, BiH lags behind on general development indicators – such as GDP per capita, Innovation Index – with respect to EU-27 countries (Table 3), and experience limited budget, institutional capacity and institutional integration⁵².

BiH is not an official member of the EU, but it entertains a close political exchange with the Union. Since 2010, BiH residents can travel to Schengen area without visa. In 2016, the country applied to enter the European Union and in 2022, BiH was granted the status of candidate country⁵³. The country progress report details the yearly improvements of the country to comply with the EU rules. In 2024, the report⁵⁴ states that BiH made none to too little progress in terms of digital transformation, agricultural and rural development.

National policies

The table below reports the main policies for smart rural areas in BiH. In 2007, BiH introduced a [Law on Agricultural, Food and Rural Development](#) (88/07). Despite its name, and some slight considerations to rural tourism and traditional rural production activities (Art. 24), the law mostly focusses on agriculture, hence missing a more holistic approach to rural development. Contrariwise, the [Strategic Plan for Rural Development of BiH \(2023-2027\)](#) sets out the political framework to rural development beyond agriculture. Adopted in 2024, the plan includes measures for rural development, support to family farms, agritourism, and local development with a budget of approx. KM 2,241 bln (EUR 1,145 bln). The plan also aims at aligning BiH agriculture with the EU *acquis* (i.e. EU rules and policies) as well as supporting agricultural modernisation in agriculture and digital innovation in rural areas.

In terms of digitalisation, the BiH Digital Country Profile⁵⁵ highlights several gaps in terms of digital accessibility, digital skills, and infrastructure. On this matter, the most relevant policies are the **Policy for Development of Information Society** and the **Electronic Communications Sector Policy**. The latter one foresees a specific measure⁵⁶ on reducing the digital divide in rural areas by stimulating the application of broadband wireless access networks and providing necessary frequency bands.

Additionally, BiH is recipient of the [Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance \(IPA\)](#), an investment policy for beneficiaries to implement political and economic reforms alongside

⁵⁰ [Global Human Settlement - Degree Of Urbanisation - European Commission](#)

⁵¹ UNPD (2013). [Rural Development In Bosnia And Herzegovina: Myth And Reality](#).

⁵² Kotevska, A, Bogdanov, N., Nikolić, A.... Petrović, L. (2015). [The Impact of Socio-Economic Structure of Rural Population On Success Of Rural Development Policy](#).

⁵³ https://enlargement.ec.europa.eu/enlargement-policy/bosnia-and-herzegovina_en full links...

⁵⁴ European Commission (2024) [Bosnia And Herzegovina Report 2024](#)

⁵⁵ ITU (2023). [Bosnia And Herzegovina – Digital Development Country Profile](#)).

⁵⁶ Measure 1.5.1: 1.5.1 Ensuring the Necessary Frequency Ranges in Order to Enable Wireless Broadband Access in Urban, Suburban And Rural Areas In Bosnia And Herzegovina, while Respecting the Principle of Technology Neutrality.

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key priorities. Competitiveness and innovation, as well as agriculture and rural development, are among the priorities.

While this document is being drafted, some provisions and amendments are being discussed on relevant laws, such as Law on Tourism⁵⁷, Law on Hospitality⁵⁸, Regulation on Conditions for Providing Hospitality Services in Rural Tourism Facilities⁵⁹, Elements for Categorization of Rural Tourism Facilities, the Law on Tourist Tax⁶⁰.

Table 10 Relevant policies for smart rural areas (Bosnia and Herzegovina)

Policy name	Aims to
<u>Law on Agriculture, Food and Rural Development (88/07)</u>	Define the terminology and set out objectives and measures for agriculture and rural development
<u>Strategic Plan for Rural Development of BiH (2023-27)</u>	Framework strategy for the modernisation of agricultural sector and rural development.
<u>Strategic Framework of the Institutions of BiH (2023-30)</u>	Structure the multi-level strategy for a prosperous, economically and socially just development
<u>Policy for Development of Information Society (2017-21)</u>	Maximise the socio-economic potential of information and communication technologies, and develop a Single Market
<u>Electronic Communications Sector Policy (2017-21)</u>	Boost the competitiveness of the ICT sector and invest into 5G
<u>Interoperability Framework of Bosnia and Herzegovina (2018)</u>	Ensure the compatibility of information systems and processes across public administration institutions

Source: Own elaboration.

The country does not have a dedicated ministry of agriculture and rural development. Instead, the **Ministry of Foreign Trade and Economic Relations** is responsible for **policies, basic principles, coordination of activities and harmonization** of the plans of the entity authorities and institutions in the field agriculture and rural development. At sub-national level, Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Water Management and Forestry, the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of the Republic of Srpska, as well as the Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of the Brcko District of BiH, steers the **direct implementation** of rural development policy. In the Federation of BiH, a part of the competence in the field of agriculture and rural development is the responsibility of the public administration units at cantonal level. Further, municipalities have a part of the competencies and obligations in implementing the rural development policy.

⁵⁷ Bulgarian Government (n.d) [Закон О Измјенама И Допунама Закона О Туризму \(С.Г.РС, Бр.16-23\) 482989354.Pdf](#) And [Broj 045.Indd](#)

⁵⁸ Bulgarian Government (n.d) [Закон О Измјенама И Допунама Закона О Угоститељству \(С.Г.РС,Бр.1-24\) 464437503.Pdf; Broj 045.Indd](#)

⁵⁹ Bulgarian Government (n.d) [Правилник О Поступку Категоризације Уг. Објеката Врсте Хостел И Објекат Сеоског Туризма \(С.Г.РС,Бр.17-24\) 495088096.Pdf](#)

⁶⁰ Bulgarian Government (n.d.) [Закон О Измјенама И Допунама Закона О Боравишној Такси \(С.Г.РС, Бр.107-24\) 355743475.Pdf](#) And [Закон О Боравишној Такси - С.Г. РС Бр. 78-11 110988726.Pdf](#)

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SMART ERA Pilot Region: East Herzegovina

East Herzegovina is a southeastern micro-region of BiH, situated in the Republika Srpska, and centered around the city of Trebinje and encompassing six municipalities: Nevesinje, Gacko, Bileća, Berkovići, Kalinovik, Ljubinje, and Istočni Mostar. Geographically, the region is mostly mountainous and comprises a rich biodiversity. Despite this natural wealth, the region is one of the least populated in BiH and it experiences persistent loss of highly educated individuals and younger, reproductive-age populations.

The critical issue affecting the rural territory of **East Herzegovina** revolves around the **undervalorisation of rural tourism and cultural and natural heritage** as drivers for economic and community development. While the region boasts significant natural assets (mountains, rivers, and landscapes) and cultural heritage (monasteries, old towns, and local traditions), these resources remain **largely untapped** due to the lack of infrastructure, digitalization, and cohesive promotion strategies (Figure 7). As a result, this rural territory is locked into a vicious cycle of **depopulation, heritage loss** and **missed economic opportunities** arising from sustainable rural tourism.

Several actors are affected by these trends, most inevitably rural residents, young people and entrepreneurs, local producers (incl. farmers), tourism organisations and local authorities. The issue affects asymmetrically this territory, producing higher consequences in remote and underdeveloped rural areas, small-scale farms, heritage sites during the entire year and even more in seasonal peak periods.

Figure 7 The vicious cycle in the Pilot of East Herzegovina. Source: Own elaboration.

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Relevant policies at Pilot level

Similarly, to the administrative layer of the BiH (national level), **there is not an official demarcation between rural and urban areas**. Consequently, statistical and other data are not classified according to this criterion. Compared to the federal level, the regional government has explicit powers to deliver rural development policies, including the economic and social revitalisation of rural areas and infrastructure⁶¹.

As shown in Table 11, the Republic of Srpska has its own **Strategic Plan for Rural Development** detailed along five strategic goals. The revitalisation of rural areas is *'one of strategic objectives that goes beyond the framework of sectorial policies and represents an integrated and comprehensive approach to development'*⁶². These strategic priorities include measures targeting economic and demographic revitalisation (incl. rural tourism and income diversification), infrastructure and service improvements (incl. via **digital** services), revitalization of the rural identity and development of **smart villages**. However, the expected targeted results in the Strategy **exclusively** refer to the agricultural sector.

Other policies deal with the digitalisation of public administration, tourism promotion and specific local development strategies. For instance, the **Tourism Development Strategy of the Republic of Srpska** identifies tourism as crucial for the economic growth of rural areas, and identifies the lack of infrastructure, limited adoption of digital tools, fragmented governance frameworks as key obstacles to attractive rural tourism.

Table 11 Relevant policies for smart rural areas in East Herzegovina

Policy name	Aims to
<u>Strategic Plan for Rural Development of Republic of Srpska (2021–27)</u>	Increase agricultural production in a sustainable way and promote the balanced development of rural areas
<u>Strategy for the digitalisation and e-Government in Republic of Srpska (2019-22)</u>	Drive the digitalisation transformation of public administration across the territory
<u>Local Agriculture and Rural Development Strategy of Trebinje (2023–27)</u>	Establish the pathway to promote agricultural development (47% of budget), resource management (12% of budget), quality of life in rural areas through better infrastructure and services, economic diversification and governance (41%)
<u>Tourism Development Strategy of the Republic of Srpska (2021–2027)</u>	Improve unexploited touristic attractions and the overall tourism value chains

Source: Own elaboration.

In the Republic of Srpska, the **Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Water Management** oversees agriculture and rural development. As rural development responsibility is interdisciplinary, it is **shared** with local government units (towns and municipalities) and most other ministries (economy, enterprise, trade, tourism, transport, communications, local

⁶¹ Bulgarian Government (n.d.) (n.d) [Cor - Bosnia-Herzegovina Agriculture](#)

⁶² Strategic Plan For The Rural Development of Republic of Srpska (2021-27).

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development, health, education, culture, family, youth, sports, labour, etc.), as well as some republican administrative organizations and institutions.

Key players

In the Pilot Region of East Herzegovina, the main challenges addressed are **depopulation**, valorisation of the **cultural, natural and gastronomic heritage**, and promotion of rural **tourism**. The underlying logic is that the development of sustainable rural tourism – based on the valorisation of local heritage – can break the depopulation cycle and boost rural revitalisation. This section provides an analysis of the main actors affected or relevant to the smart transformation of rural tourism in the Pilot area.

Figure 8 identifies the key actors in terms of typology (beneficiaries, decision makers, knowledge actor, other) and it characterises them in terms of power/resources to influence and interest in promoting rural smartification. In this area, **actors with the highest power and/or resources to influence are decision-makers and sources of authorities**, particularly Ministries and the Republic Institute for the Protection of Cultural-Historical and Natural Heritage. The only exception are municipal authorities, which, despite their role as decision makers, have only medium-level power and/or resources to drive rural smartification due to limited capacity and financial means. These actors are supposed to be the main interlocutors to drive policy change in the Pilot region.

Actors with the lowest power to influence rural smartification are those who are supposed to benefit the most from its impacts, in particular residents, farmers, rural women, rural youth and local associations. Another interesting consideration stands in the stakeholders' reason (and potential incentives) to support rural smartification in the tourism sector (Figure 8). **The biggest driver is the economic incentive, which appears relevant across several stakeholder typologies**. The second (per-importance) is knowledge, visibility and awareness.

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Figure 8 Perceived Interest and Power to influence smart rural transition in the Pilot of East Herzegovina. Source: Own elaboration.

Additionally, the analysis of the formal and informal relations (Figure 9) established between the identified actors allows us to further understand potential alliances and forces in this rural territory. **Three main stakeholders' clusters** emerge as relevant actors for smart transition of this Pilot Region: actors of the tourism value chains, decision makers and source of authority, and knowledge and cultural institutions. Clusters are sub-systems that bring those actors that have more frequent interaction; either because they belong to the same governance structure (e.g. Ministries under the same government) or because they collaborate frequently as they work on same thematic areas (e.g. culture, or tourism).

A few additional considerations can be derived. First, **municipalities are a key actor among decision makers** as they interrelate key relations with direct beneficiaries, despite they might have relatively less power/resource to drive rural smartification. Second, **actors around the tourism value chain and knowledge actors developed some more formal and regular set of exchanges**. These relations potentially provide them with an increased power to influence or drive policy change. Conversely, **direct beneficiaries from rural smartification appear less organised and not well connected to high-level decision-makers**, with an exception for farmers. Third, the **Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management**, which is the highest authority within the Republic of Sprska for rural development matters, is perceived to be disconnected from the tourism sector (e.g. missing link with rural tourism opportunities). Finally, **the potential of media involvement** – which should be understood as the amplifying voice of rural communities – **is untapped**.

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Figure 9 Perceived inter-stakeholder relations in the Pilot of East Herzegovina. Source: Own elaboration.

Policy gaps

Legislative and Strategic Gap: Key legislation and strategic frameworks are either missing or outdated, and there is a lack of national strategy for building a digital society. Telecommunications legislation is not harmonised with the EU regulatory framework, which delays alignment with the Digital Services Act, Digital Markets Act, Interoperable Europe Act, and open data policies⁶³. This legislative vacuum leaves BiH without a coordinated approach to digital transformation.

EU Acquis Gap: In rural development, the country struggles with harmonisation of regulatory frameworks and adoption of the EU acquis across different government levels⁶⁴. Weak alignment with EU regional, agricultural and digital policies exacerbates regional disparities and limits access to EU funding and support programs that could otherwise address infrastructure, innovation, and human capital deficiencies.

Data Gap: Strategic documents on rural development lack proper systems for monitoring and evaluation. Delays in establishing essential CAP-related administrative structures (such as paying agencies, control systems, and data networks) undermine policy execution.

⁶³ Ibid.

⁶⁴ Bosnia And Herzegovina Report 2024 - European Commission

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Furthermore, BiH's agricultural statistics are not fully aligned with Eurostat, complicating the comparability and effectiveness of rural policies⁶⁵.

Capacity Gap: There is a need to build stronger administrative capacities and coordination mechanisms at all levels of government. The establishment of EU-aligned institutions remains incomplete, weakening policy planning and execution.

Vertical/Horizontal Coordination: The country suffers from fragmented governance and poor coordination across state, entity, and local levels. This lack of cooperation slows reforms and limits the effectiveness of development efforts. Similar fragmentation exists in the innovation ecosystem, where shared goals among authorities are not supported by effective coordination⁶⁶.

Private Sector Development Gap: Innovation among SMEs is hampered by limited financial instruments. Government support is poorly targeted, politically influenced, and misaligned with actual SME needs. While some banks offer favourable credit terms, access to risk capital-crucial for startups and early-stage enterprises is absent. Financial mechanisms are highly segmented, lacking strategic oversight.

Tourism Gap: Many farms have not registered rural tourism as an official activity, and certain tourism types (e.g., excursion tourism) are not legally defined. Coordination among authorities, tourism operators, and community stakeholders is weak, further compounded by poor infrastructure, limited accommodation, and low digital connectivity in rural areas. Adoption of digital tools like virtual tours and online booking platforms is minimal, reducing competitiveness.

From policy opportunities to Policy Options

Key opportunities for the development of rural areas in BiH are **three-folded**: i) The **digitalisation of society and services**; ii) the **development of sustainable tourism**; and, iii) the **valorisation of rural heritage**. Based on these opportunities, the Pilot Region of East Herzegovina identified **four Policy Options** which are synthetically presented here below.

The main objective of these Policy Options is to increase the involvement of local communities in the planning and management of tourism destinations and heritage sites. Secondly, these Options seek to increase the sustainability of the tourism sector by long-term strategic planning and reinvestment for the preservation of natural resources, local knowledge and heritage. Full description of these Options is provided in Annex 2.

⁶⁵ Ibid.

⁶⁶ Strategic Plan For Rural Development Of Bosnia And Herzegovina (2023 – 2027).

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Figure 10 Policy Options for the East Herzegovina Pilot Region. Source: Own elaboration.

4.4. Finland

Finland is a **unitary non-federal state**, organised on a **decentralised** basis in three levels of governance (central, regional and local). The power of the regional self-government is quite limited, whereas most decisions are taken either at national or local level. The Finnish attention to local self-government dates to the 1860s and developed gradually since then notably with a Local Government Act. Local authorities are given both administrative and regulatory powers, and they are entitled to levy taxes, whereas regional councils -which are composed by multiple local authorities - have predominantly administrative duties⁶⁷.

Finnish rural areas cover approximately **78%** of the country surface and represent **26%** of the total population (Rural Observatory, 2021)⁶⁸. Compared to other EU countries, Finland has a very high share of **remote rural areas and population**, and the presence of very **sparsely located rural population** which makes the delivery of essential services very problematic.

The national urban-rural classification distinguishes among **four types of rural areas**, namely local centres in rural areas, rural areas close to urban areas, rural heartland areas, sparsely populated rural areas. Introduced in 2013, this typology uses grid-level data and classifies rural areas independently from their administrative boundaries, hence allowing for highly detailed analysis at spatial level⁶⁹.

In Finland, GDP per capita (in PPS) is at the same level of the EU-27 average, with almost no difference between rural and other territories. Employment opportunities in predominantly rural regions are mostly linked to the **wholesale, retail, transport, accommodation & food services, Information and Communication sector** (approx. 2 million jobs, 2023) and **industrial sector**, excluding construction (Table 3).

Finland is a **top performer** in many areas including innovation (European Innovation Scoreboard, 2025), infrastructure and digital accessibility, and digital economy and society indicators (Table 3).

⁶⁷ [Committee Of The Regions. Division Of Powers. Finland. Whole links?](#)

⁶⁸ However, note that the [Finnish official data](#) states country's rural surface equal 95% of total land and account for 31% of the overall population.

⁶⁹ Stjernberg, M., Norlén, G., Vasilevskaya, A., Tapia, C., & Berchoux, T. (2023). Scoping Report on European Rural Typologies (31.05.2023). GRANULAR. <https://doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.13767183>

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National policies

Over the last **40 years**, Finland began adopting an integrated and holistic approach to rural development⁷⁰. This long-running tradition led to a well-integrated and encompassing system, including relevant advancement in the application of **rural proofing methodologies**⁷¹. The country's rural policy '[...] can be divided into a **broad and narrow rural policy**'⁷². The broad rural policy ensures rural needs are addressed across policy areas (e.g. housing, land use, social, environment, regional, agriculture). Narrow rural policy focusses on the development of practical instruments to develop rural areas, such as the LEADER/CLLD programme, national R&D projects, village actions, funds for sparsely population areas.

Both policy branches are coordinated by a composite and multi-actor body: **Rural Policy Council**. Established in 2020, this body is led by the Minister of Agriculture and Forestry, and it is co-chaired by the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment. This Council reunites approximately 35 members from different stakeholder groups (science, policy, practice) operating at all levels, and it crosses responsibilities of several ministries.

Other networks and bodies having a relevance for the rural policy and smartification, *inter alia*, the Island Committee, the Parliamentary Body on Sparsely Populated Areas, the rural networks, and the Permanent interministerial working group for Digitalisation.

Among key policies and strategies (Table 12), the **Rural Policy Programme** (2021-27) is the main action plan of the Rural Policy Council of Finland. This programme develops along three focal points (interdependence, environmental justice, and a new knowledge-based economy) and five cross-cutting themes (sustainable use of natural resources, supporting rural actors in sustainable transition, strengthening competitiveness and vitality, ensuring smooth everyday life, and fostering inclusion and community).

Table 12 Relevant policies and strategies for smart rural areas (Finland)

Policy name	Aims to
<u>Countryside renewing with the times : Rural policy programme (2021–27)</u>	Bring together all actors involved in rural policy making along five themes.
<u>Innovation and Skills in Finland (2021-27)</u>	Support business, energy, climate, innovation, education and employment policies, as well as activities against exclusion and poverty. It includes measures of the ERDF, ESF+, JTF.
Finland's Digital Infrastructure Strategy 2025	Focus on expanding the country's digital technologies

⁷⁰ Vihinen, H. (2009). Finnish Model for Rural Policy. *Maaseutututkimus*, 17(2), 85–89; Muilu, T. (2021). Rural Policies For Sparsely Populated Areas In Finland – Old Problems, New Challenges And Future Opportunities. *European Countryside*, 13(2), 479–491. <https://doi.org/10.2478/Euco-2021-0028>; Rural Policy Council (N.D.), *The National Rural Policy Of Finland*.

⁷¹ Finnish Government (n.d.) [Säädösehdotusten Maaseutuvaikutusten Arviointi : Maaseutuvaikutusten Arviointiohje Lainvalmistelijoille - Valto](#)

⁷² Finnish Government (n.d.) [Rural Policy - Maa- Ja Metsätalousministeriö](#)

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<u>Finland's National Roadmap for the EU Digital Decade (2024-30)</u>	Provide the national plan to align with the EU's Digital Decade targets
<u>Policies for the digitalisation of education and training until 2027 (2023-27)</u>	Outline a comprehensive framework for integrating digital tools, environments, and competencies across all levels of education
<u>Finnish Digital Compass (2022)</u>	Set national targets for the effective use of digital systems and succeed in the digital transformation
<u>Islands Development Act (494/1981)</u>	Address islands and archipelago development

Source: Own elaboration.

In addition to policies presented above, the [Finnish CAP Strategic Plan](#) defines the strategic priorities in agriculture and rural development for the 2021-2027 period. Agricultural innovation and rural development are addressed through different interventions. For instance, Finland aims at achieving **100% high-speed broadband coverage** across the country by 2025, by addressing the outstanding gaps in the rural divide⁷³.

Additionally, the intended contribution to **digitalisation in agriculture** (R.3) and the **support to rural startups** (O.27) via the CAP Strategic Plan is quite remarkable (Table 13). Finland also targets **100% of its rural population via the LEADER programme** for community-led development with an allocated budget (6%) slightly exceeding the EU minimum allocation.

Table 13 Selected indicators from the CAP Strategic Plan- Finland (2023-2027)

Selected Indicators	Finland
<i>R.1 Enhancing performance through knowledge and innovation</i>	110,290
<i>R.3 Digitalisation agriculture</i>	43.83%
<i>R.39 developing the rural economy</i>	3625
<i>O.1 No of EIP operational group projects</i>	100
<i>O.23 No of supported off-farm non-productive investment operations or units</i>	428
<i>O.24 No of supported off-farm productive investment operations or units</i>	2696
<i>O.27 No of rural businesses receiving support for startup</i>	200
LEADER indicators	
<i>Population coverage</i>	2,169,107
<i>Population coverage (%) - R38</i>	100%
<i>Local Development Strategies</i>	53
<i>Preparatory Actions/Projects</i>	53
<i>Budget (€)</i>	€ 99,459,000
<i>Budget (% of EAFRD funds)</i>	6%

Source: Own Elaboration. Adapted from EU CAP Network CAP Strategic Plans Factsheets (2024) and Catalogue of CAP Intervention Dashboard

Despite that the country's CAP Strategic Plan does not develop a national definition for **Smart Villages**, it secured a € 10 million budget for the 2023-2039 period to finance

⁷³ European Commission (2024). [At a glance: Finland's CAP Strategic Plan](#).

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community-led innovation in rural areas via smart village projects/strategies) with a dedicated measure: **Smart Villages Collaboration**. This measure aims at financing projects increasing *‘the vitality of the village or a municipality in a very concrete way’* by building a common project and financing its practical implementation on one or more specific issues⁷⁴. In addition to this measure, the LEADER-specific intervention and general investment interventions can finance collaborative smart village projects and investments costs linked to their implementation.

Table 14 Smart Villages in approved CAP Strategic Plan - Finland

Finland	
Definition	There is no national definition. The Finnish CAP Strategic Plan uses the definition provided by the European Pilot Project on Smart Eco-social villages supported by the European Commission (2018): “Smart Villages are communities in rural areas that use innovative solutions to enhance their sustainability and resilience based on local strengths and opportunities.” (Finnish CAP Strategic Plan, p. 970-971)
Dedicated interventions	Smart Village Collaboration (Cooperation Projects - 07, COOP)
Other Interventions	LEADER (77-05, COOP); Investments in rural environment development (Inv. General Benefit 04, INVEST)
R40	60
Budget	Smart Village Collaboration Projects (Cooperation 07, COOP): 10.000.000 € [2023-2039 period]; Cooperation – Smart Village Projects (strategies): Estimated 60 projects at average 166 000 € / Smart Village Project (strategy); Preparation funding: Estimated 10 feasibility studies at 5000€ lumpsum/study.

Source: Own elaboration adapted from Smart Rural 27 (2024). Finnish Factsheet.

In Finland, the **Cohesion Policy** is defined mainly at central level, through national Operational Programmes. The table below reports the planned allocations to CLLD, ITIs and other territorial tools as across the planned Operational Programmes in areas which are non-urban (Table 15). As shown in the table, Finland does not allocate any funds for **CLLD explicitly for rural areas**⁷⁵. Second, some other territorial tools are used in the Finland Structural Funds Programme, and Innovation and Skills in Finland Operational Programmes to target non-urban areas. However, Managing Authorities have mostly indicated no territorial targeting, with a slight exception for some actions targeted to sparsely populated areas. The Cohesion Policy potential to address intra-country and intra-regional territorial divides is hindered without a clear earmarking of these resources to rural territories.

Table 15 Contribution to rural development from the national Operational Programmes of Cohesion Policy - Finland (2021-2027)

Operational Programme Name	Specific Objective(s) Targeted:	Total contribution (million €)	Territorial code
Finland Structural Funds programme 2021-2027 (ERDF, ESF+)			

⁷⁴ Smart Rural 27 (2024). [Smart Villages in CAP Strategic plan Finland. Factsheet.](#)

⁷⁵ Though some costs are foreseen in relation to general CLLD implementation and running costs/facilitator for the specific policy objectives on Europe Closer to Citizens (RSO5.2) and Social Europe (MSO3.1) but no territorial codes were used.

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<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	RSO1.3; RSO4.1; RSO4.7	€ 13.44	33 (No territorial targeting)
Innovation and Skills in Finland (ERDF, ESF+, JTF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	RSO1.1; RSO1.2; RSO1.3; RSO2.1; RSO2.6; RSO3.2; RSO4.1; RSO4.7; RSO4.8	€ 736.39	31 (Sparsely populated areas)
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	RSO2.1; RSO1.2; RSO1.3; RSO2.1; RSO2.4; RSO2.6; ESO4.7; ESO4.8; JSO8.2	€ 2,155.55	33 (No territorial targeting)
Total Budget for CLLD (non-urban areas)			€ -
<i>Of which CLLD for rural areas</i>			€ -
Total Budget for ITIs and other territorial instruments			€ 2,905.38
<i>Of which to rural areas</i>			€ 736.39

Source: Own elaboration, adapted from Cohesion Open Data (2025).

Over the 2021-27 period, Finland allocates **€ 10.80 million** (which is approximately 7.7% of the country's EMFAF budget) to contribute to sustainable blue economy and community-led fisheries and aquaculture activities in both coastal and inland areas⁷⁶. In total, Finland will provide funding to 11 FLAGs (6 coastal FLAGs, 5 inland FLAGs), which is one more compared to the 2014-2020 programming period.

SMART ERA Pilot Region: Northern Ostrobothnia

Northern Ostrobothnia is classified under NUTS3 level as it is part of the North & East Finland region (NUTS2). The SMART ERA Pilot Region covers the three rural municipalities, Alavieska, Kalajokki and Nivala, in the Nordic peri-urban area having a **strong entrepreneurial ecosystem** for small and medium-sized enterprises. Northern Ostrobothnia stands out with its **high level of technological infrastructure and digital readiness**, unlike the other SMART ERA Pilot Regions.

However, as other rural areas in Finland, the main challenges affecting this Pilot Region are **negative demographic trends, economic stagnation and limited access to essential services**. These issues have been developing over several decades, driven by demographic shifts, economic restructuring, and technological evolution. The problem has become increasingly visible since the 1990s. Structural causes such as the shift towards more global economy and the progressive disruption and loss of economic activities in rural areas are the origins of these negative trends.

The consequences of such trends have generated lower job opportunities, more emigration, and the decrease in basic services due to the lack of a sizeable population. Transport is a particular challenge in this region, which has **very low population density**. Long distances affect residents' ability to access essential services as well as the capability of firms to reach out customers and connect their actors from their value chains.

⁷⁶ European Commission (2025). CLLD Factsheet 2021-2027: Finland.

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These issues do not exist in isolation but rather reinforce and exacerbate each other, creating a cascading effect that impacts well-being, economic resilience, and social sustainability. While some areas have been affected more than others, the impact continues to grow, making it imperative to assess how these issues will evolve in the future.

WHAT and WHY

Figure 11 The vicious cycle in the Pilot of Northern Ostrobothnia. Source: Own elaboration.

This vicious cycle seriously impacts rural residents, in particular elderly and youth, which are obliged to adapt to longer traveling distances to reach services or workplaces. Local entrepreneurs, SMEs, farmers and workers of the primary sectors also struggle due to inadequate infrastructure and restricted market reach. Limited budget constraints municipal authorities and service providers to cut down services especially in more remote territories, and territories which are suffering the most from the loss of traditional sectors.

Relevant Policies at Pilot level

Table 16 summarises other relevant policies and strategies contributing to smarter rural areas in this Pilot area. Above all, the **North Ostrobothnian Regional Programme** identifies **three long-term objectives** to guide the long-term development (by 2050) – good living environments, inhabitant at the core, thriving regional economy – and **four focus areas** for short-term implementation (2022-25). ‘Digitalisation’ is one of these focus areas, which emphasises Industry 4.0, the smart use of data and digital platform economy. A second focus area is the ‘supply of sufficient workforce’, which includes measures for addressing ageing population, urbanization and competence development.

Other strategies outline the policy opportunities for rural areas to develop. For instance, innovation and digitalisation are also targeted by the regional **Smart Specialisation strategy**; the regional **Roadmap for Tourism** underlines the key role of rural tourism for the growth of the regional tourism industry (so far quite underdeveloped); and the **Climate Roadmap** emphasises possibilities in relation to nature and forest management,

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bioeconomy, and innovative transport and energy systems. Furthermore, the **Northern Ostrobothnia Transport System Plan** aims at ensuring an adequate level of transport connection in sparsely populated areas. Most of the below-mentioned regional strategies focus on entrepreneurial and business expansion of the region. Lower-level strategies have also been developed by municipal authorities in the area covered by the SMART ERA Pilot Region but unfortunately it lacks of a strategy for inter-municipal cooperation.

Table 16 Relevant policies and strategies for smart rural areas in Northern Ostrobothnia

Policy name	Aims to
<u>North Ostrobothnia Regional Programme (2022-25)</u>	Promote long-term growth and welfare in the Region by combining a strategic plan for 2040 with actionable projects for a four-year period which touches relevant topics for community innovation (e.g. economic growth, education & skills, community engagement, innovation ecosystems, digitalisation, bio- and circular economy, energy transition, and mobility)
<u>Northern Ostrobothnia Transport System Plan 2040</u>	Ensure vitality of the region and the accessibility to skilled labour and productive investments. The plan targets road maintenance and sufficient accessibility in sparsely populated areas.
<u>Oulu Region Smart Specialisation Strategy (2021–25)</u>	Focuses regional innovation strategy on: (1) Renewable & healthy; (2) Climate-smart; (3) International & networked region.
<u>Ostrobothnia Tourism Roadmap for 2030</u>	Develop the region's tourism potential, including rural tourism. Digitalisation and data are targeted to boost tourism planning and experience.
<u>Climate Roadmap 2021-30</u>	Outline the path towards carbon neutrality. It links to smart bioeconomy, forest and natural resource management, and agriculture as potential for carbon sink, low emissions transport and energy production.
Alavieska municipality strategy	Transform the municipality into a modern, child-friendly and entrepreneur-friendly context with good local services. Priority areas: 1. Resident comfort and well-being, 2. Local services, 3. Entrepreneurship and business, 4. Branding
<u>Kalajoki municipality strategy</u>	Create a vibrant city and attracting investments and tourism. Priorities are attracting investments; services and quality of every day's life; housing; climate.
Nivala Municipal strategy	Boost services for residents, foster local businesses and promote local sustainability.

Source: Own elaboration.

Key players

In the course of the SMART ERA project, this Pilot Region will focus on the potential of **platform economy** to connect rural service providers and rural users, hence boosting, on one hand, the delivery of services and goods to rural residents, and, on the other hand, facilitating SMEs and microenterprises in connecting with local demand.

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An analysis of key players, their power/resources to influence and interests (Figure 12) and relations (Figure 12) are presented below. It emerges that actors with the **highest power and resources** to enhance smart rural transition are institutional bodies operating at different levels (municipal, regional, national, EU) and public-private partnerships; universities; and media. Conversely, direct and indirect beneficiaries of smart rural development have very limited resources and power to engage with these matters.

In terms of incentives, the overall framework is quite diversified (Figure 12). The most 'powerful actors' are mostly incentives by **political consensus and legislative development/compliance**, on one hand, and **knowledge and cooperation**, on the other hand. Economic incentives are very relevant to ensure that the local businesses, farmers and industrial sectors, as well as mobility, technological and energy providers are engaged in this process.

Figure 12 Perceived Interest and Power to influence smart rural transition in the Pilot of Northern Ostrobothnia. Source: Own elaboration.

Among these actors, it is possible to distinguish **four main clusters of relations** (knowledge actors, actors engaged in international cooperation, supra-local public institutions; and the private sector) (Figure 13). There are a few considerations we can draw from the analysis. **Knowledge actors are quite well connected among themselves**, and pursue **relevant relations** with the private sector, supralocal public institutions, and actors/projects active in international cooperation.

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The private sector emphasised set of relations with academia and the public institutions is not by any surprise, as this region distinguishes itself for a rich entrepreneurial ecosystem and more political engagement are around making the regional economy even more vibrant. Less clear is the linkages between local actors, farmers, associations and beneficiaries, probably also due to geographical remoteness.

Figure 13 Perceived inter-stakeholder relations in the Pilot of Northern Ostrobothnia

Policy gaps

Funding and Investment Gap: Urban and coastal areas benefit from modern, diversified economies, while rural regions remain reliant on declining primary industries such as agriculture and forestry. Investment gap is particularly strong with respect to Urban centers like Helsinki, Tampere, and Oulu attract most public investments (EU/national), widening the divide with rural regions in transport, services, energy, and climate adaptation, digitalisation.

Legislative and Strategic Gap: Although policy frameworks acknowledge rural challenges, they often lack the financial tools and mechanisms necessary for effective municipal-level implementation.

Innovation Accessibility Gap: While digitalisation is promoted, existing strategies do not offer sufficiently tailored smart solutions for rural business, transport, and service delivery needs.

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Tourism Gaps: The North Ostrobothnian Strategy for Tourism recognises tourism potential but fails to fully integrate digitalisation into broader rural economic development efforts.

Governance Gaps: development strategies operate in isolation, with limited coordination between municipalities and sectors, reducing efficiency and innovation.

From policy opportunities to Policy Options

According to this Pilot Region, smart community-led innovations can help rural areas to address existing gaps, leveraging on existing and upcoming opportunities. In particular, **four opportunities** were identified.

First, the emergence of **localised digital platforms and digital services hubs**, whose contribution can serve to centralise service planning and provisioning (leveraging on AI-driven data analytics) while promoting decentralised local economies based on SMEs and microenterprises involvement. Second, the development of **collaborative business models**, such as collaborative rural networks for mobility, to pool resources, skills and people together, creating economy of scale even in more remote areas. Third, **citizen-driven governance models** for wider community engagement thanks to the progressive uptake and expansion of digital engagement platforms. Last, the use of **cross-border cooperation** with Nordic countries facing similar challenges and living in a comparable ecosystem. Based on these policy opportunities, this SMART ERA Pilot Region identified two Policy Options (Figure 14), which are further detailed in Annex 1.

Figure 14 Policy Options for the Northern Ostrobothnia Pilot Region.

4.5. Italy

Italy is a **unitary decentralised republic**, organised along **four levels of governance**: regions (20 in total, of which 5 with special autonomy), metropolitan cities (14) and provinces (93), and municipalities (7,900)⁷⁷. Regions have a relevant role in the country, as each of them has their own status, which determines the form of governance and internal organisation of the region⁷⁸. Contrariwise, the role of provinces has been progressively decreased over the past decades, in favor of regions, metropolitan cities and municipalities⁷⁹.

⁷⁷ Cotella, G. (2021): Country Profile of Italy. Hannover. = ARL Country Profiles. <https://www.arl-international.com/knowledge/country-profiles/italy/rev/3770>. Last access: 9/10/2025.

⁷⁸ CoR - Italy Introduction

⁷⁹ Pizzetto, F. (2015). La Legge Delrio: Una Grande Riforma In Un Cantiere Aperto. Il Diverso Ruolo E l'opposto Destino Delle Città Metropolitane E Delle Province. AIC Rivista; De Nonno, M. (2019). La riforma del governo locale nella legge Delrio: qualche riflessione cinque anni dopo. Federalismi.it. ISSN 1826-3534. <https://hdl.handle.net/11392/2407665>

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Rural areas cover more than **60%** of the country's surface (with an almost equal share between remote rural areas and rural areas close to cities) and **17%** of the national population (Rural Observatory, 2021). As in the case of BiH, a large part of the rural territory in Italy is also **mountainous**, hence have specific characteristics in terms of altitude, steepness and micro-climate, which impacts its accessibility and socio-economic activities in these areas.

Italy defines **three types of rural areas**: rural areas specialised in intensive agriculture, intermediate rural areas and rural areas with development problems. These typologies are addressed via its national CAP Strategic Plan. Since 2012, a second typology has existed at national level and defines the so-called '**inner areas**', which are areas characterised by significant distances from essential services. Covering 4,000 municipalities and 13 million of people, inner areas are classified in intermediate inner areas, remote inner areas, and ultra-remote inner areas. In 2022, a revision of the methodology to classify inner areas applied different thresholds to distinguish between the three subcategories⁸⁰. Development patterns and marginalisation trends are not the same across different rural areas and across Italian regions⁸¹. It is therefore very important to understand differences and commonalities for policy action.

The degree of urbanisation and population density in Italy is above EU-27 average (Table 3). Digitalisation of the economy and society is **overall slightly below** the EU-27 average, and the country is considered a **moderate innovator** (Table 3). However, as per rural areas, Italy experiences large in-country differences, both at territorial and regional levels.

In terms of the economy, the Italian **GDP is slightly below the EU-27 average**, with major differences across territories. Notably, GDP in PPS in rural areas is a fifth of the one in predominantly urban areas and a fourth of the overall value in intermediate regions⁸². **Employment** in predominantly rural regions is by far associated with **non-market services** (i.e. public administration, education, health, arts, extraterritorial organisations, other), followed by the **industrial sector** (Table 3).

National policies

Italy does not have a **national rural development** policy as such that does not derive from an EU agricultural and regional development policy (CAP, Cohesion Policy). However, other strategies target the general or thematic development of some rural areas. Since 2014, the country has a specific strategy – the **National Strategy for Inner Areas** – to address the marginalisation of **inner areas** (which do not represent the entirety of rural areas). In 2025, the **National Strategy for Green Communities** was launched to valorise natural capital in

⁸⁰ Openpolis (2024). [Che cosa sono le aree interne - Openpolis](#). In practice, no changes in the overall number of inner areas but intermediate inner areas are now areas far at least 27.7 min from essential services poles (vs. 20 min before), remote areas if distance exceeds 40.9 min (vs. 40 min before) and ultra-peripheral if exceeding 66.9 min (vs. 75 min before).

⁸¹ Annunziata, A., Scorza, F., Corrado, S., & Murgante, B. (2024). Unveiling intra-rural divides: investigating decline and prosperity in rural areas. The case study of southern Italy. *European Planning Studies*, 32(7), 1478–1505. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2024.2335312>

⁸² Rural Observatory (2023). GDP in PPS.

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rural areas through productive value chains. This strategy is grounded on **Law 221/2025** which provides the legislative framework to establish and support ‘green communities’, or to say local municipalities engaged in the ecological transition and sustainable management of natural resources.

The main **Ministries** relevant for the rural development are the Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forestry, and Ministry of European Affairs, South, Cohesion Policy and PNRR.

Table 17 Relevant national policies and strategies for smart rural areas (Italy)

Policy name	Aims to
National Strategy for Green Communities (2025)	Enhance the natural capital of rural and mountain areas – water, forests and landscape – through forestry, tourism, water, tourism, construction, circular economy, mobility, agriculture; and promoting a new relationship of subsidiarity and cooperation with urban areas
<u>Strategy for Technological Innovation and Digitalisation (2025)</u>	Promote digitalisation and innovation in the country in an inclusive and sustainable way. Rural areas are not mentioned in the body of the strategy, but an action aims at increasing innovation in small municipalities (‘borghi del futuro’)
<u>National Strategic Plan for Inner Areas (2025)</u>	Identify main intervention areas for the national strategy for inner areas (transport, education, health, local development). Innovation (social, technological, organisational) is foreseen in these areas.
<u>National Strategy for Digital Competences (2021)</u>	Increase digital competences, hence removing the gap to other EU countries and in-country territorial divide. No mention to rural areas.
<u>National Strategy for Inner Areas (2014)</u>	Revitalise areas far from the provision of essential service and other poles and counter depopulation
National Strategy for Sustainable Development (2017, 2022)	Develop a framework for the delivery of the Agenda2030 and Sustainable Development Goals. Under the ‘planet’ priority, the strategy aims to enhance High Natural Value areas and reinforce urban-rural linkages of environmental ecosystems. The Strategy has been declined into strategies at regional and metropolitan levels.
<u>Law 221/2015 on Green Economy and Natural Resource Use</u>	Promote green economy, while limiting the overuse of natural resources. It offers a legislative basis for municipalities interested to implement ecological transition

Source: Own elaboration.

The **Italian CAP Strategic Plan (2023-27)** sets out the country’s objectives and measure to modernise the agricultural sector and promote rural development. In this document, Italy attempted to put a specific attention to the promotion and sharing of knowledge and innovation (Table 18), as to overcome the fragmentation of innovation practices (in AKIS) and low level of digitalisation⁸³.

Community-led local rural development is financed **above the EU minimum threshold** (6% instead of 5% of EAFRD funds), however, it is estimated that these finances cover only 56% of the rural population. This share is significantly lower than what predicted in other analysed

⁸³ European Commission (2025). At a glance: Italy’s CAP Strategic Plan.

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countries (e.g. Finland, 100%; Slovenia- 90% using the same share of budget allocation). This disparity becomes even more evident when considering the number of intended projects and strategies financed through national allocations, which is higher in Italy in absolute terms, although these initiatives are more targeted and smaller in scale.

Table 18 Selected indicators from the CAP Strategic Plan- Italy (2023-2027)

Selected Indicators	Italy
<i>R.1 Enhancing performance through knowledge and innovation</i>	541,430
<i>R.3 Digitalisation agriculture</i>	<0.05%
<i>R.39 developing the rural economy</i>	8,856
<i>O.1 No of EIP operational group projects</i>	833
<i>O.23 No of supported off-farm non-productive investment operations or units</i>	4,006
<i>O.24 No of supported off-farm productive investment operations or units</i>	5,185
<i>O.27 No of rural businesses receiving support for startup</i>	398
LEADER indicators	
<i>Population coverage</i>	41,310,153
<i>Population coverage (%) - R38</i>	55.80%
<i>Local Development Strategies</i>	108
<i>Preparatory Actions/Projects</i>	38
<i>Budget (€)</i>	€ 422,363,290
<i>Budget (% of EAFRD funds)</i>	6%

Source: Own Elaboration. Adapted from EU CAP Network CAP Strategic Plans Factsheets (2024) and Catalogue of CAP Intervention Dashboard.

The national CAP Strategic Plan also allocates **€ 64 million** to implement **469 Smart Villages projects/strategies** in 10 Italian Regions⁸⁴ (Table 19). Unitary project budget can vary considerably, going from € 26,000 to € 2.8 million, depending on the project size and regions where the project occurs.

Smart villages are financed via a **dedicated measure** (SRG07), which aims at financing the preparation and implementation of integration Smart Villages project and strategies for cooperation thematic areas (employment, social inclusion, innovation, circular bioeconomy, quality of life, planning, participation and local capacities). Additionally, the LEADER intervention (SRG06) allows to finance the implementation of Smart Villages innovations across the country, including within those regions which did not activate the SRG07 measure. In the country, cooperation and knowledge exchange among Smart Villages is facilitated by the National Rural Network with the '[Smart Rural Hub](#)' initiative.

Table 19 Smart Villages in approved CAP Strategic Plans - Italy

Italy	
Definition	n/a
Dedicated interventions	Cooperation for rural, local and smart villages (SRG07, COOP)

⁸⁴ Basilicata, Campania, Liguria, Lombardia, Marche, Piemonte, Sicilia, Toscana, Umbria, Veneto.

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Other Interventions	LEADER – Implementation of local development strategies (SRG06, COOP)
R40	469
Budget	Total amount (2023-2029): € 64.526.985,70 [Out of which EU contribution: € 27.924.400,36]. The unit amounts range from €26,000 (for small projects) to €2,800,000 (big project) depending on regions.

Source: Own elaboration adapted from Smart Rural 27 (2024). Italy.

In Italy, **Cohesion Policy** is articulated along thematic National Operational Programmes and Region-specific Operational Programmes. The table below reports an analysis on the planning of national resources for CLLD, it is and other territorial tools in non-urban areas (Table 20). It emerges that CLLD and ITIs are not planned through National OPs, and other territorial tools are not territorially targeted.

Table 20 Contribution to rural development from the national Operational Programmes of Cohesion Policy - Italy (2021-2027)

Operational Programme Name	Specific Objective(s) Targeted:	Total contribution (million €)	Territorial code
NP Culture 2021-2027 (ERDF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	RSO 1.2; RSO1.3; RSO2.1; RSO2.4; RSO4.6	€ 632.00	33 (No territorial targeting)
NP Health 2021-2027 (ERDF, ESF+)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	ESO4.11; RSO4.5	€ 601.25	33 (No territorial targeting)
NP Just Transition Fund (JTF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	JSO8.1	€ 1,162.83	32 (Other types of territories targeted)
NP Research, innovation and competitiveness for green and digital transition 2021-2027 (ERDF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	RSO1.1; RSO1.2; RSO1.3; RSO1.4; RSO1.6; RSO2.2; RSP2.3	€ 5,420.68	33 (No territorial targeting)
NP School and skills 2021-2027 (ESF+, ERDF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	ESO4.5; ESO4.6; ESO4.7; RSO4.2	€ 3,662.64	33 (No territorial targeting)
NP security for legality 2021-2027 (ERDF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	RSO1.2	€ 228.23	33 (No territorial targeting)
NP Social inclusion and poverty reduction 2021-2027 (ESF+, ERDF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	ESO4.3; ESO4.8; ESO4.9; ESO4.10; ESO4.11; ESO4.12	€ 3,119.41	33 (No territorial targeting)
NP Youth, women and jobs 2021-2027 (ESF+)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	ESO4.1; ESO4.2; ESO4.3; ESO4.4	€ 5,000.63	33 (No territorial targeting)
Total Budget for CLLD (non-urban areas)			€ -
<i>Of which CLLD for rural areas</i>			€ -

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Total Budget for ITIs and other territorial instruments	€ 19,827.67
<i>Of which to rural areas</i>	-

Source: Own elaboration, adapted from Cohesion Open Data (2025).

However, the analysis of Regional Operational Programmes shows that CLLD and ITIs are planned at regional level, with specific earmarking for rural areas, mountains or sparsely populated areas⁸⁵.

Additionally, **10.52% of the national EMFAF budget** (€ 103.81 million) are allocated to finance Fisheries Local Action Groups to valorise community-led development in Small-Scale Coastal Fisheries, encompassing sustainability of production chain, sustainable tourism, mitigation and adaptation to environmental changes and safeguard of marine biodiversity⁸⁶. Overall, Italy plans to finance 29 FLAGs, all of which located in marine and coastal areas.

SMART ERA Pilot Region: Valle di Sole, Trentino

Valle di Sole is a remote and peripheral area in the northwestern part of the Autonomous Province of Trento. This area is characterised by sparse population and mountainous territory. Valle di Sole counts **13 municipalities**, with a total resident population of **15,470 inhabitants** (2022). The valley's economy is significantly based on **tourism**, both in summer and winter, followed by **livestock farming** and **forestry**.

Throughout a number of co-creation and community engagement activities, Valle di Sole decided to focus its actions on the **shrinkage of the dairy farming sector** in its mountainous territory (Figure 15). In between 1982 and 2010, the number of agricultural farms with livestock in this area per 1,000 inhabitants dropped from 66.3 to 12.5⁸⁷. Indeed, the alpine dairy sector faces a significant crisis, driven by a combination of economic, environmental, and structural challenges. The decline of dairy farming over time led **landscape degradation and increased natural risks** on one side, and **economic stagnation and depopulation** on the other hand. This trend causes other considerable challenges, such as the loss of local knowledge, low territorial distinctiveness and degradation of the built environment.

These trends began in 70s, with increased focus on the tourism sector, and since 90s, with increased intensification of agricultural practices throughout the province (apples, wine) and legislative requirements on food quality despite producers' size. **Actors that bear the most negative costs** of this trend are the dairy sector and farmers, other primary sector producers; the local community; the tourism sector, and the natural environment. The impacts are higher in inner municipalities, such as those in Valle di Sole, and areas which are still reliant on traditional dairy farming including alpine mountain farmhouses.

⁸⁵ IFEL (2024). *Le Strategie territoriali nella politica di cohesion 2021-2027. Agenda territoriale nazionale e ruole dei comuni italiani*. Edizione Ottobre 2024; Further data currently being updated in the Strat-Board platform.

⁸⁶ European Commission (2025). CLLD Factsheet 2021-2027: Italy.

⁸⁷ SMARTERA (2025). Pilot needs and gap analysis. Updated in May 2025.

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Figure 15 The vicious cycle in the Pilot of Valle di Sole. Source: Own elaboration.

Relevant Policies at Pilot level

Due to its specificities and complex challenges, Valle di Sole is considered as a **"peripheral or ultraperipheral area"** and it is part of the **Italian National Strategy for Internal Areas (SNAI)**. The inner areas strategy for the Valle di Sole was established in 2016 as the second project area for the province of Trento, initiated following the approval of the Partnership Agreement 2014-2020 for the use of European structural and investment funds. Selected interventions from this strategy receiving funding from the state and European structural funding (with an equal split between the two). The Province of Trento coordinates the actions carried out in its territory through a governance committee.

The second most relevant strategy for rural development is the **Provincial Plan for Rural Development**, which is the place-based strategy of EAFRD funds transposed at provincial level. In addition to these, other strategies address partially local development, community participation, and/or rural land management (Table 21).

Table 21 Relevant policies and strategies for smart rural areas in Valle di Sole

Policy name	Aims to
<u>Provincial Plan for Rural Development (2022-27)</u>	Support rural development intervention at provincial level and complement the national CAP Strategic Plan
<u>Inner areas strategy for Valle di Sole (2019-24)</u>	Counteract marginalisation and demographic decline in 'inner areas' through a place-based approach
<u>Sectoral Plans for Forest Management, within the Research</u>	Strengthen public policies support to research and innovation in i) competitiveness of the Trentino economy; ii) promoting employment growth

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<u>and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation (2021-27)</u>	
<u>Provincial Sustainable Development Strategy</u>	Promote an integrated sustainable development of rural, mountainous and urban areas
<u>Provincial Youth Area Plan</u>	Activate actions in favour of young adults (aged between 11-29)

Source: Own elaboration.

Key players

In SMART ERA, Valle di Sole will seek possibilities to co-create smart solutions which can address the interlinked challenges of its primary sector (primarily dairy sector), and natural and local ecosystems. According to involved stakeholders, **several actors should be involved in the process** as they have the **highest level of power and resources** to lead this change (Figure 16). They include different stakeholder types, going from primary sector producers, actors of the food value chain, governmental institutions (all levels), natural parks, the chamber of commerce, and vocational training centres and schools.

Breeders, producers and primary sector workers – which are the direct beneficiaries of smart solutions – oppose resistance to unconditionally adopting new methods, such as digitalisation and innovative technologies, seen as complex or threatening to traditional practices and have a certain scepticism towards environmental regulations, fear that policies do not consider the realities of small businesses. **Actors from the food value chain** also resist to promote local products widely due to the lack of uniform product quality, higher product costs and difficulties in large-scale distribution. **Governmental actors** are perceived as sustaining a level of political bias and favouritism towards interest groups.

Rural families and youth are perceived to have the lowest capacity and resources to influence the system, though their presence in the area is fundamental to avoid further depopulation and ensure presence of workers to nurture the dairy sector.

The primary incentive to encourage actor participation are **monetary/economy incentives**, though legal compliance and legislative development, and knowledge and cooperation are equally important for some stakeholders (Figure 16).

Among identified actors, there is quite a complex level of intra and cross-stakeholder relations (Figure 17). The existence of close intra-stakeholder relations emerges in five thematic areas, resulting in **five informal clusters of interactions**: the dairy sector; the agri-food supply chain; promotional actors (mostly tourism sector and natural parks); the supra-local public sector; and users.

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Figure 16 Perceived Interest and Power to influence smart rural transition in the Pilot of Valle di Sole. Source: Own elaboration.

Figure 17 Perceived inter-stakeholder relations in the Pilot of Valle di Sole. Source: Own elaboration.

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Policy gaps

Legislative and strategic Gap: digital and innovation strategies often exhibit territorial blindness, failing to adequately account for regional specificities and local development needs. This misalignment undermines the effectiveness of localised policy interventions.

Vertical/horizontal Coordination Gap: weak collaboration across institutional levels undermines the effectiveness, accountability, and inclusiveness of rural development strategies in Trento and similar regions. Significant fragmentation in innovative systems, e.g. AKIS, and in the design and execution of strategies. This limits coherence and the potential for synergies across sectors and levels of governance.

Data Gap: lack of disaggregated, accessible data hampers the monitoring and evaluation of policies. While the policy landscape in the Autonomous Province of Trento aligns well with national and EU rural development objectives, the pilot analysis reveals persistent shortcomings in transparency and accessibility of monitoring data in rural policies.

Participation Gap: There is a noticeable gap in structured stakeholder engagement mechanisms, which weakens participatory policy design and reduces the relevance and legitimacy of implemented measures.

Policy Coordination Gap: Although several instruments show potential for cross-policy synergies, these remain largely underutilised due to fragmented implementation and weak integration frameworks.

Tools Gap: There is a need for operational tools, such as digital platforms and open-data systems, to support more effective and equitable implementation of policies-particularly in addressing asymmetric territorial impacts.

From policy opportunities to Policy Options

The Pilot Region of Valle di Sole envisions to revitalise the local economy, in full swing with natural preservation and community engagement. To this end, this territory aims at exploring the opportunities that **digitalisation**, and **valorisation of ecosystem services** from the agricultural and forestry sector, and **slow tourism** can provide for rural development. Activation of the local community is understood as a cross-cutting enabler to support such smart transition.

Within this framework, Valle di Sole identified **five Policy Options** (Figure 18), of which two are related to community engagement (in particular in relation to youth), two are related to the nature and ecosystem services valorisation, and two are crosscutting enabling options based on data collection to improve policymaking based on evidence. These Policy Options are described in Annex 2.

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Figure 18 Policy Options for the Valle di Sole Pilot Region.

4.6. Slovenia

Since the independence from Yugoslavia (1991), Slovenia is **decentralised unitary state** organised in **two levels** (national, local). Despite the attempt to create an intermediate level (regional or provincial), as envisaged in the Constitution, this has never happened due to the limited size of the country, the existing apparatus, and other local interests⁸⁸. However, the country has twelve statistical regions and two cohesion Regions (East and West Slovenia), whose only purpose is statistical and to absorb regional development funds⁸⁹.

Slovenia has 212 municipalities, of which **201 are not urban**⁹⁰. Municipalities have competencies on local affairs on issues affecting its residents, and they raise money via their own tax revenues, non-tax revenues, revenues from the management of municipal property and tangible financial assets, grants, and transferred revenues from the national budget and EU funds⁹¹.

The country distinguishes **three types of territory**: suburban areas, typical rural areas and depopulation areas⁹². For the delivery of the LEADER programme funding (CAP 2023-2027), rural areas are all settlements with less than 10 000 inhabitants (Table 3).

At national level, **rural land surface** is in line with the EU-27 average (approximately 75% of the total surface), with a stronger presence of remote areas close to cities (51%) than remote rural areas (24%) (Table 3). However, the share of rural population of the country's residents is higher than the EU-27 average, reaching approximately **45% of the total population** and mainly located in rural areas close to urban centres (Table 3).

⁸⁸ Hacek, M., Kukovič, S. (2020): Slovenija, država pestrih regionalnih delitev (Slovenia, country of diverse regional divisions). *Lex Localis*, 2020, 13-39.

⁸⁹ Marot, N. (2024): Country Profile of Slovenia. Hannover. = ARL Country Profiles. <https://www.arl-international.com/knowledge/country-profiles/slovenia/rev/4203>. Accessed on 15/10/2025.

⁹⁰ CoR - Slovenia

⁹¹ *Ibid.*

⁹² Perpar, Anton & Matija, Kovačič. (2002). Typology and development characteristics of rural areas in Slovenia. Dela. 10.4312/dela.17.85-99.

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Slovenia experiences **stark regional and territorial disparities** in employment, wellbeing, and digitalization, with West Slovenia being one of the more developed regions and East Slovenia among the less developed ones.⁹³ The national GDP per capita is slightly below the EU-27 average (Table 3). Predominantly rural regions generate employment mostly in the **industrial sector** (construction excluded), followed by **non-market services** (education, public administration, health, other) (Table 3).

Additionally, all selected DESI indicators are also below the EU-27 average, with stronger differences in terms of digital skills (Table 3). According to the European Innovation Scoreboard, the country is a **moderate innovator**, but the region in which the SMART ERA Pilot is situated is a strong innovator.

National policies

As per other countries analysed in this study, Slovenia does not have a self-standing national policy or strategy for rural development. Rural development is addressed via the EU policies of the CAP and Cohesion Policy, handled by the respective Ministries. However, specific mentions to rural areas are available in several thematic policies and strategies.

Already in 2004, the **Spatial Development Strategy** defined the need to boost rural attractiveness and vitality. The diversification of economic activity, in line with the comparative advantages of rural areas, is targeted by this strategy to create conditions for people to stay and thrive in rural areas. Urban-rural linkages through service provision, preservation of rural traditional and natural heritage, tourism development and teleworking in rural areas are equally targeted. Unfortunately, rural areas are defined narrowly as 'zone outside urban areas' (p.11) and a rural settlement is defined as an *area 'more than 500 inhabitants and at least 10 percent of the population engaged in agricultural activity as family workforces and/or employees in family farms'* (p.12)⁹⁴.

The old **Digital Strategy 2020**, targeting the digitalisation of Slovenia society, has a separate chapter on **smart cities and communities**. In the same strategy, a **Network of Non-Governmental Organisations for an Inclusive Information Society** is launched to ensure that technology fits the needs of communities (and not the opposite).

The newer **2030 Digital Strategy** keeps its focus on **smart communities**, which '*need to be encouraged to take a systematic approach to digital transformation. The goal of deploying smart cities and communities must be based on the governance of integrated entities, moving beyond silo governance. System solutions, platforms, and solutions based on common data models, unified standards, open data, and real-time data are needed*' (pp 39.40)⁹⁵. For the development of smart communities, the training of local authorities and governance integration at the national level are envisaged. The strategy also envisages the

⁹³ OECD (2020). [Regions at a Glance. Slovenia](#); OECD (2024). [Regions at a Glance: Slovenia](#); [Cohesion regions in Slovenia | GOV.SI](#)

⁹⁴ Slovenian Ministry of the Environment, Spatial Planning and Energy, Spatial Planning Directorate (2004). [Spatial Development Strategy of Slovenia](#).

⁹⁵ Government of the Republic of Slovenia (2023). Strategy for Slovenia's Digital Transformation by 2030.

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reduction of **rural-urban digital gap** in connectivity, and it foresees the creation of **Rural Digital Innovation Hubs**.

Highly interestingly for community development and unique across analysed countries is Slovenia's attention to the **non-profit sector**. This emphasis is integrated into a specific strategy and related Act for the **development and professionalisation of the non-governmental sector**, with the aim of deinstitutionalizing and promoting community care at the local/regional level (Table 22). The strategy foresees an NGO Development Fund for the long-term financing of NGOs, and the NGO Council as an expert consultative body.

Table 22 Relevant policies and strategies for smart rural areas in Slovenia

Policy name	Aims to
<u>Strategy for Slovenia's Digital Transformation by 2030 (2023-30)</u>	Promote Slovenia's digital transformation. Specific attention to rural areas is mentioned in the text.
<u>Strategy for the Development of the Non-Governmental Sector and Volunteering (2023); Act on NGOs</u>	Increase the professional structure of NGOs for the improvement of community care at different governance levels
<u>Slovenian Tourism Strategy (2022-28)</u>	Develop tourism industry in a more sustainable and comprehensive manner
<u>Industrial Strategy for green, creative and smart development (2021-30)</u>	Ensure the competitiveness of the economy and create conditions for restructuring the industry balancing economy, environment and society. Rural areas slightly mentioned in relation to digital connectivity
<u>Our food, rural areas and natural resources beyond 2021</u>	Provide public support to food production/processing and to rural development, addressing rural features and need
<u>National Environmental Action Programme 2020–30</u>	Provide long-term direction for the protection of the natural environment
<u>Transport Development Strategy until 2030</u>	Develop a more integrated and effective transport model. Rural areas are marginally mentioned
<u>Active Ageing Strategy (2017)</u>	Formulate responses and policies to demographic change and ageing. Adjustment transport options to ensure equal opportunity to access transport in rural areas is foreseen
<u>Spatial Development Strategy (2004)</u>	Define spatial development as a polycentric urban system developed along system of centres (national/regional/inter-municipal)
Local Self-Government (Art 138-144 of the Constitution); Act on Local Self-Government	Guarantee and frame the structure, functions, and governance of municipalities, which are the basic units of local self-government

Source: Own Elaboration.

The **Slovenian CAP Strategic Plan (2023-27)** addresses innovation in the agrifood sector and more generally in rural development. Table 23 provides selected indicators related to knowledge and innovation activities financed through the CAP. Slovenia planned to allocate **6% of its EAFRD funds to the LEADER programme** (above the mandatory threshold of 5% EAFRD funds allocation). This budget is intended to cover 90% of the rural population and finance 37 local development).

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Table 23 Selected indicators from the CAP Strategic Plan- Slovenia (2023-2027)

Selected Indicators	Slovenia
<i>R.1 Enhancing performance through knowledge and innovation</i>	83,336
<i>R.3 Digitalisation agriculture</i>	4.30%
<i>R.39 developing the rural economy</i>	986
<i>O.1 No of EIP operational group projects</i>	60
<i>O.23 No of supported off-farm non-productive investment operations or units</i>	576
<i>O.24 No of supported off-farm productive investment operations or units</i>	2,163
<i>O.27 No of rural businesses receiving support for startup</i>	-
LEADER indicators	
<i>Population coverage</i>	1,218,053
<i>Population coverage (%) - R38</i>	90%
<i>Local Development Strategies</i>	37
<i>Preparatory Actions/Projects</i>	0
<i>Budget (€)</i>	€ 35,542,556
<i>Budget (% of EAFRD funds)</i>	6%

Source: Own Elaboration. Adapted from EU CAP Network CAP Strategic Plans Factsheets (2024) and Catalogue of CAP Intervention Dashboard

Smart Villages are clearly defined, however there are no dedicated interventions, budget or result indicator to support them in the CAP Strategic Plan (Table 24). This is quite surprising given the fact that Smart Villages were initiated and strongly promoted by the Slovenian Member of the European Parliament Bogovic. Smart Villages might be supported by the Community-led Local Initiative (CLLD) programme which receives 1% of all Cohesion Funds, even though no binding legal earmark to deliver this instrument⁹⁶.

Table 24 Smart Villages in approved CAP Strategic Plans - Slovenia

Slovenia	
Definition	A rural community that uses innovative solutions and digital technologies to improve economic, social or environmental challenges.
Dedicated interventions	n/a
Other Interventions	LEADER (IRP26)
R40	24
Budget	n/a

Source: Own elaboration adapted from Smart Rural 27 (2024). Slovenia.

In Slovenia, **Cohesion Policy** is articulated by the means of National Operational Programmes. Table 25 below details the planning of national resources for CLLD, ITIs and other territorial tools in non-urban areas. Some resources are targeted to CLLD beyond urban areas, though this measure is not clearly allocated to a specific territorial code. More substantial resources are planned for other territorial tools.

⁹⁶ Smart Rural 21. What's happening in my country. [Slovenia – Smart Rural Areas](#). Accessed on 15/10/2025.

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Table 25 Contribution to rural development from the national Operational Programmes of Cohesion Policy – Slovenia (2021-2027)

Operational Programme Name	Specific Objective(s) Targeted:	Total contribution (million €)	Territorial code
Slovenia's EU Cohesion Policy Programme 2021-2027 (ERDF, ESF+, CF, JTF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to CLLD</i>		€ 40.11	16 (CLLD - Other types of territories targeted)
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>		€ 216.70	24 (Other territorial: Other types of territories targeted)
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>		€ 3,839.66	33 (No territorial targeting)
Total Budget for CLLD (non-urban areas)			€ 40.11
<i>Of which CLLD for rural areas</i>			€ -
Total Budget ITIs and other territorial instruments			€ 4,056.36
<i>Of which to rural areas</i>			-

Source: Own elaboration, adapted from Cohesion Open Data (2025).

In the EMFAF (2021-2027), Slovenia allocates € 12.26 million to FLAGs via the CLLD mechanism⁹⁷, which equals over **36% of the entire EMFAF country budget**. In total 6 FLAGs are financed in the same period (one more than in 2014-20), of which only one marine and five inland FLAGs.

SMART ERA Pilot Region: Šmarje-Padna

The SMART ERA Pilot Region covers the villages Šmarje and Padna, which are situated in the rural littoral of Slovenia. They both have an important **historical and strategic role** within the Istria region. Notably, Šmarje has been historically known as a crossroads in Istria as it connects more than 20 neighboring villages in the region and three countries (Slovenia, Italy and Croatia). Additionally, due to available public services and infrastructure, the village of Šmarje is an important social rural development hub.

On the other hand, Padna is situated on the end of the ridge, with steep slopes of terraces, where 'cultura mista' type of crop is grown. Economy of the village is strongly based on services such as trade, accommodation, and transport that are generated by activities at the port of Koper. Both villages have participated in **Smart Villages** projects in the last year and had links with the EU Strategy for the Alpine Region (EUSALP) and the LAG Istra.

Since mid of the 20th century, rural population had declined severely due to a massive farmland abandonment and rural exodus. This trend partially changed in the last 25 years, with the rural lifestyle seeming to become attractive again. Young families decide to remain or even immigrate to rural areas. Unfortunately, a large part of traditional local heritage has been lost and many **structural conditions** for people to stay in the long-term are lacking.

⁹⁷ European Commission (2025). [CLLD Factsheet 2021-2027: Slovenia - Oceans and fisheries](#)

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Notably, both villages face similar challenges, and these are primarily linked to the lack of **public transport options**, progressive **environmental degradation** due to overdependence on private vehicles, and **limited economic dynamism** as result of limited accessibility to goods and services, as well as to other actors along the value chain (Figure 19). Different actor groups are affected by these trends, in particular **older generations** and **people not using/having access to a personal vehicle** (e.g. children and teenagers), **local farmers and agri-food operators**, and the **tourism sector**.

WHAT and WHY

Figure 19 The vicious cycle in the Pilot Šmarje-Padna. Source: Own elaboration.

Since **2020**, Smart Village initiatives have attempted to address some of these challenges, but implementation has been slow. This Pilot Region envisions that, by developing new and rural-proofed solutions/services to primarily improve connectivity, accessibility and attractiveness of the area, and participatory approaches, it will be able to create new public places, shared activities in recreational areas, as well as in creation of new jobs (e.g. sustainable tourism and farming).

Relevant Policies at Pilot level

Local partners in this Pilot Region could not identify existing policies and strategies with a fundamentally positive/negative impact on smart rural transformation besides the measures of the CAP and Cohesion Policy. The LEADER programme was highlighted as particularly important, especially for the **Local Action Group Zelena Istra**.

Key players

Figure 20 illustrates key players for the smart transition of this Pilot Region, as described and identified by the lead partners of this Pilot in collaboration with local actors. The ministries, municipal authorities, transport service providers and public-private partnership around rural mobility and digital transformation are perceived to have the **highest power**

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and resources to influence the process. The main interests driving their action are economic incentives and political/territorial development. A wide range of other stakeholders have an **intermediate capability** of nurturing this transition, though the interests are not always converging. Finally, the **least capable** of influencing this process are those actors expected to benefit from the results, in particular citizens, elderly people, new rural residents, urban dwellers.

Figure 20 Perceived Interest and Power to influence smart rural transition in the Pilot of Šmarje-Padna. Source: Own elaboration.

In parallel, Figure 21 illustrates the perceived interactions across identified stakeholders. As clearly visible and outstanding in comparison to other SMART ERA Pilot Regions, is the presence of **rural smartification cluster**. This cluster is composed of actors and organisations with experience in smart rural areas (either from a practice and/or theoretical point of view). This cluster is well connected with institutions and the local community.

Relevant is the **institutional clusters**, grouping those actors able to plan and deliver policies at different governance levels and enjoy higher resources/power. However, these actors might have **conflictual political agendas** on certain matters (e.g. Municipality of Koper and Piran). Other relevant actors are the **tourism** sector, and the **transport sector**, which however, seem to be less connected to decision-makers and beneficiary groups. **Urban dwellers** are perceived as a relevant actor, as the might benefit from increased connections with their rural hinterland, despite being interconnected with other relevant groups.

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Figure 21 Perceived inter-stakeholder relations in the Pilot of Šmarje-Padna. Source: Own elaboration.

Policy gaps

Governance Gaps: Although various policies address rural development and mobility, there are shortcomings in governance frameworks—particularly in enabling innovative, community-led initiatives and ensuring their long-term viability.

Vertical/horizontal coordination: Existing policies tend to operate in silos, with limited mechanisms to ensure the long-term sustainability of mobility and digitalisation solutions proposed at the community level.

Financing Gaps: There is a lack of long-term financing mechanisms to support community-led initiatives in rural areas, limiting the scalability and continuity of promising pilot projects and local initiatives.

From policy opportunities to Policy Options

This Pilot Region decided to focus its activities on (i) sustainable mobility services and sustainable tourism development; and (ii) community engagement in circular economy and in green and sustainable shared activities. The underlying hypothesis is that **ICT tools** offer opportunities for development of **intergenerational transport solutions** and **agri-environmental and consulting services** to support local investments in rural areas.

Additionally, key **policy opportunities are expected to come from enhanced local engagement** in sustainable activities like circular economy, environmental education, and

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smart transport. Notably, **participatory open innovation approach** will result in generating additional revenue for raising the local quality of life regarding the most vulnerable groups of people. Co-creation tools like **SEROI+** methodology⁹⁸ will be also used to assess the social, economic and environmental impacts of decision-making.

In connection with this opportunity, the Šmarje/Padna Pilot Region developed a Policy Option around the topic of Digital Mobility. This is detailed in Annex 2.

Figure 22 Policy Options for the Šmarje/Padna Pilot Region.

4.7. Spain

Since 1978, Spain is a **decentralised country**, composed of three levels of government (state, regional, local). Compared to other EU countries, Spanish regions (i.e. the 17 Autonomous Communities) enjoy a considerable autonomy both in terms of legislative framework and fiscal competences⁹⁹.

The rural population equals **13% of the total country population**, and it is spread across **73% of the national surface**. About two thirds of rural inhabitants are located in areas close to cities, and the remaining one third in remote rural areas. This is even though half of the rural areas are considered peripheral. Spain's degree of urbanization is indeed above the EU average (Table 3).

Law 45/2007 identifies rural areas as villages and towns with less than 30,000 residents and a population density below 100 inhabitants per km²¹⁰⁰. The same law **categories rural areas** in three subgroups: rural areas to be revitalised, intermediate rural areas, and peri-urban rural areas¹⁰¹. However, in the CAP 2023-37, the EAFRD for rural development did not follow this typology for fund allocation, but rather specific definitions or criteria according to the intervention of Autonomous Regions¹⁰².

In economic terms, Spain has an overall **GDP per capita** slightly below the EU-27 average (Table 3) with stark differences between rural and/remote rural areas, and other areas¹⁰³. Predominantly rural regions generate employment mostly in the **industrial sector** (construction excluded), followed by **non-market services** (education, public administration, health, and others) (Table 3). In terms of employed people, the two main

⁹⁸ [SEROI+ – Social Environmental Economic Return on Investment Methodology direct links???](#)

⁹⁹ De Gregorio Hurtado, S.; Tomàs, M. (2022): Country Profile of Spain. Hannover. = ARL Country Profiles. <https://www.arl-international.com/knowledge/country-profiles/spain/rev/3839>. Accessed on 13/10/2025.

¹⁰⁰ OECD (2020). Rural Well-being. Geography of opportunities. Country note. [Spain](#).

¹⁰¹ Stjernberg, M., Norlén, G., Vasilevskaya, A., Tapia, C., & Berchoux, T. (2023). Scoping report on European rural typologies. GRANULAR. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13767183>

¹⁰² EU CAP Network (2024). CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027. Key figures and fact. Spain.

¹⁰³ Rural Observatory (2023). GDP per capita in PPS. Predominantly urban: 1.07 Mio in PPS; Predominantly rural close to a cities: 27.88k in PPS; Predominantly rural remote 18.72k in PPS.

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sectors in predominantly rural regions are **wholesale, retail, transport, accommodation & food services, Information and Communication** and **non-market services** (Table 3).

In terms of innovation and digital transformation, the country has quite a diverse picture. Level of digital skills – both basic and above basic – is higher than the EU-27 level and fixed broadband speed is well beyond the EU average (Table 3). However, mobile broadband speed is lower than the EU average, in particular in rural areas (Table 3). Overall, Spain is considered to be a **moderate innovator** according to the DESI.

National policies

Spain does not have a unified national policy for the development of rural areas. Rural development is – however – addressed through the implementation of the EU policies (CAP, Cohesion Policy). Additionally, specific challenges and topics are addressed via **national strategies**.

Table 26 lists the most relevant policies and strategies at national level. Among these, it is worth highlighting two main legislative and strategic policy frameworks. First, the Spanish **national strategy** to address **demographic change and depopulation**, which coincided with the creation of the Secretary General for the Demographic Challenge (2020) under the Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge. This strategy is detailed in its [General Guidelines](#) and [Action Plan](#). The plan translates the overall vision into **130 measures** which range across infrastructure investment, digitalisation, local business support, and sustainability. Second, Spain is among the first European countries integrating **rural proofing** into a national law (27/2022). The law indicates the mandatory definition of a 'Mechanism for Rural Guarantee' which shall abide to the assessment of territorial effects of public policies on rural areas through specific methodology. To date, **9 out of the 17 Autonomous Communities incorporated** (or planned to) **rural proofing** in their regional legislation¹⁰⁴.

Rural areas appear in other sector strategies, such as around the digitalisation and resilience of the agri-food sector, mobility, climate and environment, and social economy. Additionally, as said above, Spanish regions have specific legislative competences. As a result, some of the Autonomous Communities approved or launched specific legislative frameworks to strengthen rural development. An example is **Castilla-La Mancha's** Law 2/2021 and its interlinked regional strategy to combat rural depopulation, the **Catalan** Rural Agenda and High Mountain Law, and **Castilla y Leon's Strategy** for Demographic and Territorial Sustainability¹⁰⁵.

¹⁰⁴ REDR (2024) [Rural Proofing en España – Rural Proofing](#)

¹⁰⁵ Rural Pact (n.d.) [Spain | Rural Pact Community Platform](#) ; Berga, X., Claramunt, B. (2024). [The Catalan Law of the High Mountain \(preliminary\)](#). MOVING EU Foresight Workshop.

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Table 26 Relevant policies and strategies for smart rural areas in Spain

Policy name	Aims to
<u>Evaluation of Public Policies Law 27/2022</u>	Provide a legislative framework for the evaluation of public policies. A mechanism for rural guarantee (rural proofing) is included in the text
<u>2030 National Strategy for the Demographic Challenge</u>	Advance social and territorial cohesion and fight against depopulation via a coordinated approach
<u>Spain Digital 2026</u>	Ensure 100% of the population, including rural and hard-to-reach areas, has connectivity of at least 100 Mbps
<u>National Food Strategy</u>	Establish sustainable food system and achieve open strategic autonomy along the food value chain. Resilience and sustainability of rural communities is specifically targeted.
<u>Strategy for the Digitalisation of the Agri-Food and Forestry Sector and Rural Environment</u>	Increase digital transition in the agri-food and forestry sectors in rural areas, by reducing territorial divide, increasing use of data, and promoting emergence of new businesses
<u>Technical Assistance Programme for Agri-food cooperatives 2025</u>	Supports innovation, digitalisation, and generational renewal in the agri-food sector
<u>Plan to promote the social economy (2024-25)</u>	Promote social economy sector and organisations, actors and initiatives operating in this field
<u>Climate Change and Energy Transition Law 7/2021</u>	Guide energy transition and climate mitigation and adaptation in Spain. Rural areas are recognised both in light of their specific needs as well as their carbon sink potential
<u>Strategy for Secure, Sustainable and Connected Mobility 2030</u>	10-year framework for the development of the transport sector in Spain. Mobility in rural areas and smart mobility are both included among priority areas.
<u>Law 45/2007 and Royal Decree 752/2010</u>	Establish measures to favour the sustainable development of rural areas

Source: Own elaboration.

The **national CAP Strategic Plan** also targets the modernisation and development of rural areas as identified in Table 27. Notably, Spain targeted above 1 million people to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange or participation in EIP Operational Groups (R.1), which is well beyond other analysed countries. In relation to these, the number of envisaged **EIP operational Groups** is quite high compared to other country studied (O.1) as well as new rural businesses (R.39). Additionally, Spain allocates **twice the minimum EU budget to LEADER** (10% of its EAFRD funds) to support more than 200 Local Development Strategies and around 50 preparatory actions/projects. However, this amount is largely insufficient to reach all of its rural population.

Table 27 Selected indicators from the CAP Strategic Plan- Spain (2023-2027)

Selected Indicators	Spain
<i>R.1 Enhancing performance through knowledge and innovation</i>	1,165,582
<i>R.3 Digitalisation agriculture</i>	3.23%
<i>R.39 developing the rural economy</i>	58,699
<i>O.1 No of EIP operational group projects</i>	851
<i>O.23 No of supported off-farm non-productive investment operations or units</i>	904

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O.24 No of supported off-farm productive investment operations or units	1,422
O.27 No of rural businesses receiving support for startup	86
LEADER indicators	
Population coverage	22,332,464
Population coverage (%)- R38	56.30%
Local Development Strategies	207
Preparatory Actions/Projects	49
Budget (€)	€ 516,654,229
Budget (% of EAFRD funds)	10%

Source: Own Elaboration. Adapted from EU CAP Network CAP Strategic Plans Factsheets (2024) and Catalogue of CAP Intervention Dashboard

Smart Villages are planned only by the Autonomous Community of Galicia in the country, though a specific measure which foresees the support of 16 Smart Villages strategies for an approximate budget of 750 EUR/operation. However, other regions can still support Smart Villages via other measures for cooperation and investments.

Table 28 Smart Villages in approved CAP Strategic Plans - Spain

Spain	
Definition	n/a
Dedicated interventions	Non-productive investments in basic services in rural areas (6872) (Specific intervention title for Galicia region: Digitization. Smart villages (GAL6872_06))
Other Interventions	Investment aid for agricultural diversification (6864, INVEST); Cooperation for the structuring of the territory (7163, COOP); Aid for investments in agricultural infrastructure to promote competitiveness (6843.2, INVEST)
R40	72
Budget	€750.00/ operation, total budget not specified in CAP SP

Source: Own elaboration adapted from Smart Rural 27 (2024). Spain.

In Spain, Cohesion Policy is defined through a number of nation-wide Programmes and specific regional Operational Programmes. Table 29 identifies national programmes which allocated financing to CLLD, ITIs or other territorial tools to non-urban areas. As shown in the table, **territorial codes** have been used to identify resources directed to rural, mountainous, sparsely populated areas or islands. **No rural CLLD is identified in national programmes**, whereas this might occur at regional level.

Table 29 Contribution to rural development from the national Operational Programmes of Cohesion Policy – Spain (2021-2027)

Operational Programme Name	Specific Objective(s) Targeted:	Total contribution (million €)	Territorial code
Employment, Education, Training and Social Economy (ESF+)			
Of which dedicated to other territorial tools	ESO4.1; ESO4.3	€ 24.90	28 (Other approaches: Rural areas)
	ESO4.1; ESO4.3; ESO4.3; ESO4.5; ESO4.6; ESO4.7	€ 3,531.06	33 (No territorial targeting)

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ESF+ Social Inclusion, Child Guarantee and Fight Against Poverty (ESF+)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	ESO4.8; ESO4.11	€ 13.80	28 (Other approaches: Rural areas)
	ESO4.8; ESO4.9; ESO4.10; ESO4.11; ESO4.12	€ 1,966.97	33 (No territorial targeting)
ESF youth employment (ESF+)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	ESO4.1; ESO4.4; ESO4.8	€ 1,730.07	33 (No territorial targeting)
Just Transition Spain (JTF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	JSO8.4	€ 52.12	28 (Other approaches: Rural areas)
	JSO8.3	€ 108.29	29 (Other approaches: Mountainous areas)
	JSO8.2	€ 25.32	30 (Other approaches: Islands and coastal areas)
	JSO8.1	€ 92.84	31 (Other approaches: Sparsely populated areas)
	JSO8.0	€ 20.99	32 (Other approaches: Other types of territories targeted)
	JSO8.1	€ 626.11	33 (No territorial targeting)
Pluri-regional Programme Spain (ERDF)			
<i>Of which dedicated to other territorial tools</i>	RSO5.2	€ 18.04	20 (Other territorial: Rural areas)
	RSO5.2	€ 18.04	23 (Other territorial: Sparsely populated areas)
	RSO1.5; RSO2.4; RSO2.5; RSO2.7	€ 1,150.18	28 (Other approaches: Rural areas)
	RSO2.1; RSO2.2; RSO2.3; RSO2.4; RSO2.7; RSO3.1	€ 659.66	30 (Other approaches: Islands and coastal areas)
	RSO1.1; RSO1.2; RSO1.3; RSO1.6; RSO2.1; RSO2.2; RSO2.3; RSO2.7; RSO3.1	€ 10,251.12	33 (No territorial targeting)
Total Budget for CLLD (non-urban areas)		€	-
<i>Of which CLLD for rural areas</i>		€	-
Total Budget for ITIs and other territorial instruments		€	20,289.51
<i>Of which to rural areas</i>		€	2,163.19

Source: Own elaboration, adapted from Cohesion Open Data (2025).

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Spain allocates a total of € **150.34 bln to CLLD in FLAGS** (approximately **9.6%** of the national EMFAF budget for 2021-2027)¹⁰⁶. This budget will be used to enhance the sustainability of the marine and maritime sectors, and notably to finance 44 coastal FLAGS (8 more than in the 2014-20 period). CLLD will complement to create synergies between sectors, particular in fields such as biotechnology, renewable energies and tourism, and boost training and the development of new technologies.

SMART ERA Pilot Region: Soller/Tramuntana

This Pilot Region is situated in Mallorca, the largest Balearic Islands (Spain) and the seventh largest in the Mediterranean Sea. Sóller is a charming rural town in northwest Mallorca Island at approximately 30 km from the capital of Mallorca, counting a population around 14,000 inhabitants. This town is a popular tourist destination known for its rich **cultural and natural heritage**, nestled in a valley surrounded by the Tramuntana mountains. Its economy is mainly based on **agriculture** and **tourism**. In 2020, this pilot area hosted 169 agricultural exploitations covering around 670 hectares (less than 4 hectares per farm on average). Whereas the tourism capacity is equivalent to half of the residents, divided between tourism establishments (3,159 beds) and registered vacation houses (3,313)¹⁰⁷.

This municipality is facing diverse challenges (Figure 23). One of the main ones is **massification of tourism**, which increases the burden on infrastructure, services, and community cohesion. This generates conflicts over resource use and **socio-economic inequalities** among the resident and tourist population, as well as among economic sectors. Around one fifth of Sóller population is international and has a high-income and advanced age (+50 years old). This is causing two main social issues: a perception of loss of cultural identity by local population, and a tremendous increase in property prices that is also contributing to the loss of young people moving to other more affordable cities and villages. According to statistics published by one of the largest online real estate platforms in Spain, the average price registered a **266% increase** compared to ten years ago¹⁰⁸. Socio-economic inequalities contribute to the **decline of talented youth** who seek better opportunities abroad whereas second homeowners and tourists flow into the region.

Weak collaboration between local sectors, in particular agriculture and tourism, exacerbates this trend. **Digitalisation** – if further developed – is perceived as a solution to enhance cross-sector management of resource stocks and flows, and social cohesion. To date, digital connectivity in the Region is very deficient, as well as the provision of digital services by public authorities or companies.

¹⁰⁶ European Commission (2025). CLLD Factsheet 2021-2027: Spain.

¹⁰⁷ SMART ERA (2025). Pilot needs and gap analysis. Updated version.

¹⁰⁸ *Ibid.*

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<u>PIAT-Plan d'Intervenció en Ambits Turístics (Consell de Mallorca)</u>	An island-wide land-use and tourism planning instrument that zones and limits tourist accommodation and regulates saturated areas
<u>Programa de Asistencia Técnica Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de España 2025</u>	Reinforce the agri-food sector through: i) cooperative cooperation, ii) competitiveness, iii) Spanish agri-food cooperative socio-economic observatory.
<u>Mallorca local Participatory Development Strategy (2023-27)</u>	Enhance well-being, transformation, and sustainability in rural communities as part of the LEADER programme
<u>The RIS3 (Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation) of the Balearic Islands (2021-27)</u>	Foster innovation, economic transformation, and sustainable development in the region. The strategy prioritises digitalisation, sustainability, and the integration of traditional sectors with emerging technologies
<u>Open-data & digital government (Government of the Balearic Islands)</u>	Enable municipal reuse/sharing of datasets and standardised digital procedures
<u>Destination Sustainability Plan</u>	Guide tourist destinations toward environmental, socio-economic, and territorial sustainability
<u>Low Emission Zones</u>	Reduce traffic's environmental impact, prioritise local drivers, convert parking spaces into resident-only green zones

In addition to the list above, other relevant initiatives include the [Mallorca Activa: Rural SME Accelerator Office](#) for the revitalization of productive sector in municipalities with less than 20,000 inhabitants, as part of the national Accelerate SME programme coordinated under the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation. This office functions as a digital transformation hub for SMEs, self-employed workers, and entrepreneurs in rural areas of Mallorca. It offers business advisory services, basic and advanced digital training, business model support, access to grants, and the creation of local business directories. It also supports priority objectives such as entrepreneurship, the Sustainable Development Goals, and the promotion of strategic sectors.

Key players

In alignment to the challenge defined by this Pilot Region and their specific vision for rural development, Figure 23 maps the main actors with a stake in the transition. Alongside the **Sóller municipality** and specific **Regional Government Departments**, several actors from the **tourism, agrifood and mobility sectors** have been identified as highly influential due to their power or resources.

Tourism and the **hospitality sector** are perceived as being a very influential sector, as able to capture financial resources coming from abroad, with strong ability to impact on the island's economy. Alike, farmers and agrifood cooperatives have moderate influence on the current situation and have some resistance to adopt modern farming practices.

Inter and cross-relations between stakeholders are mainly organised via sectors/thematic clusters (Figure 25). **Cross-relations** between sectors and identified clusters are poorly coordinated and/or quite conflictual. Remarkable is the presence and level of **local residents and civil society** (170 registered active associations in the area), which is a result of the size and severity of conflicts in this area.

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In this overall landscape, some stakeholders **have different roles** (in particular bigger associations or larger businesses) being at the same time delivery actor, knowledge actor (through specific expertise) and potential beneficiaries of smart island transition. For instance, the train company of Sóller is perceived as a key actor to drive the transition, but also as a potential beneficiary from increased transition from the use of private vehicles to public transport.

Figure 24 Perceived Interest and Power to influence towards smart rural areas in the Pilot of Sóller/Tramuntana

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Figure 25 Perceived inter-stakeholder relations in the Pilot of Sóller/Tramuntana

Policy gaps

Legislative and Strategic Gap: Public policies and services are inadequately tailored to the specificities of Sóller. Issues like the regulation of vacation rentals, classification of urban gardens, and tourist flow management remain insufficiently addressed.

Policy Stability Gap: Frequent changes in government and policy direction undermine continuity in long-term development strategies, generating uncertainty among residents and stakeholders and weakening the implementation of consistent planning.

Vertical/Horizontal Coordination: Lack of vertical alignment and collaboration between local and regional administrations in monitoring and managing tourism and mobility. This has led to the failure of initiatives like the Palma App and traffic information screens. Further, tourism, mobility, agriculture, and cultural sectors operate in silos, limiting cooperation and the development of integrated local solutions.

Data Gap: significant lack of standardised, disaggregated, and real-time data across key sectors (tourism, mobility, agriculture). Infrastructure such as sensors and integrated data platforms is missing or underutilised. There are no mechanisms or platforms enabling cross-sectoral or intra-sectoral data sharing. This prevents coordinated service delivery, joint marketing, and comprehensive planning across tourism, agriculture, and culture.

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Digital Tools and Skills Gap: Digital innovation is hindered by low digital literacy and limited availability of smart tools. Local actors lack training in digitalisation and data management.

Water Management Gap: Water scarcity is a pressing issue, yet there is insufficient monitoring of water inflows and usage. Lack of sensor-based systems to assess reserve levels constrains sustainable water resource management.

Tourism Development Gap: Local authorities lack the tools, data, and planning capacity to effectively manage and redistribute tourist flows, leading to overtourism during peak seasons. At the same time, tourists are often unaware of local realities and more sustainable tourism and cultural offerings. This is also due to the lack of a coordinated strategy and platform to make this offer more accessible to visitors and resident population.

Wealth distribution gap: The wealth of the municipality is not equally distributed across the territory, its sectors and stakeholders, resulting in a handful of businesses concentrating the large majority of tourist incomes. This also results in few local stakeholders retaining all the power and decision-making for the whole territory, which also exacerbates the tensions.

Mobility Gap: Mobility challenges are worsened by poor public transport options and high car ownership rates. Lack of investment in effective transport solutions exacerbates congestion and environmental impacts.

Small-Agriculture Development Gap: Due to land classification laws, many small farmers are not recognised as professionals and are excluded from subsidies and legal markets. This fosters informal economic activity and discourages young farmers.

Digital Agriculture Regulation Gap: Strict national and regional drone regulations (e.g., weight limits, spraying bans) hinder the adoption of precision agriculture. Sóller's UNESCO protection status adds bureaucratic complexity.

From Policy Opportunities to Policy Options

For this Pilot Region, **digitalisation** is a key opportunity to address challenges and deep tensions faced in this territory. Smart community-led innovations could contribute to breaking sectoral silos through improved **data-sharing frameworks** and fostering **mutual understanding between sectors** and **governance levels**, allowing for co-designed strategies and stronger community cohesion.

As such, the Sóller /Tramuntana region already identified **three Policy Options** that provide the legislative and operational framework for these innovations to develop. These Policy Options primarily target the tourism sector in its intersection with quality of life of both visitors and local residents, environmental protected and more broadly, a more coordinated framework for governing innovation and policy change (more details in Annex 2).

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Figure 26 Policy Options for the Sóller /Tramuntana Pilot Region.

5. Key results

This chapter presents an aggregated and comparative view of findings from the previous sections on EU and sub-level policies for community-led rural innovation (also referred to as ‘smart rural areas’ or ‘smart rural communities’). The main highlights of each section are synthesised here below.

Results from the EU-level analysis

At EU level, there are **six main policy frameworks** explicitly relating to community-led rural innovation, namely: the CAP, Cohesion Policy, EU’s research and innovation programme, European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF), New EU Bauhaus, the EU’s Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas (LTVRA). Under these policy frameworks, **dedicated policy instruments** have been designed and support community-led rural innovation.

Some of these policy instruments exist simultaneously in several frameworks, such as the **LEADER/CLLD** programme (in the CAP, Cohesion Policy, EMFAF, LTVRA), or **AKIS/EIP Operational Groups** (in EU’s Research and Innovation Programme, CAP, New European Bauhaus, LTVRA), or **Smart Villages** (CAP, Cohesion Policy). Other policy instruments also exist but they might not be used consistently or insufficiently to promote community-led or rural innovation (e.g. Smart Specialisation Strategies, CLLD and Integrated Territorial Investments in Cohesion Policy) or might be novel and hence needing to pass impact evaluation for future uptakes (e.g. Startup Villages, Rural Pact, Rural Action Plan).

The **LEADER programme** is the most relevant policy instrument for community-led rural innovation in terms of historical and spatial evolution, and budget allocation (€ 5 bln)¹⁰⁹. Its relative success led to the upscaling of this approach in other policies (Cohesion Policy, EMFAF). Nevertheless, it is staggering the asymmetry in the allocated budget across policy frameworks. Notably, the Cohesion Policy allocates less than € 400 million to CLLD in rural areas despite allocating twice the CAP budget for rural development.

The above-mentioned policy frameworks and instruments are correlated to **existing concepts** (Living Labs, Smart Villages, Startup Villages, LEADER/CLLD, Smart Specialisation) which contributed to the evolution of smart rural areas or smart territories. These concepts operate at different territorial scales, and they might (or not) being enshrined in existing legislative texts. Understanding nuances allow to finetune related policy instruments in the future, avoiding overlapping and promoting synergies.

Countries where SMART ERA Pilot Regions are situated

This report carries out in-depth policy analysis in the six countries where the SMART ERA Pilot Regions are situated (Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Finland, Italy, Slovenia and

¹⁰⁹ LEADER programme (2023-2027): covering 65% of EU-27’s rural areas, approximately € 5 bln (7.7% of EAFRD budget).

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Spain). A comparative analysis of contextual and specific indicators proves the **heterogeneity of rural areas** across selected countries, in terms of rural population, rural surface, innovation and digitalisation level, and socio-economic situation¹¹⁰. The **share of rural and remote rural areas** significantly impacts some countries (e.g. 70% of Finland's surface are remote rural areas), implying strong differences in policy design. In five countries, **most job opportunities do not come from the agricultural, forestry and fishing sectors**, but rather from the industrial sector; wholesale, retail, transport, accommodation & food services, Information and Communication; and non-market services (e.g. education, health etc.). Only in Bulgaria, most rural jobs come from the agriculture, forestry and fishing sector.

Of all sample countries, **Finland** performs better both in terms of innovation and digitalisation. Relevant are **in-countries differences** (NUTS2 level), showing that regions – where SMART ERA Pilots of Italy and Slovenia) – are located outperform their national average in terms of innovation. **Granularity of data and indicators** is crucial to incorporating these differences into policy making. The Rural Observatory provides indicators on rural and remote rural areas, but only at country level, whereas most other EU indicators (e.g. DESI, EIS, RIS) do not allow them to distinguish between rural and non-rural areas.

Results from national policies and strategies in selected countries

Our analysis shows a **diverse degree of integration of rural and community initiatives into national policy frameworks**. Overall, rural needs are mostly targeted through traditional **rural development policies** (particularly Cohesion Policy and CAP, see section below), whereas other sectoral policies or strategies on digitalisation, innovation, industrial/entrepreneurial development, health etc. often **lack a territorial approach**. This undermines the development of place-based policies and their ability to address the specific needs and opportunities of rural areas.

The level of rural integration into public policies differ strongly, ranging from countries having a **long-lasting history** of integrated rural policies (e.g. Finland), to countries with a few targeted policies and strategies (e.g. **National Strategy for Inner Areas** and **National Strategy for Green Communities** in Italy; **National Strategy for the Demographic Change** – Spain; **National Digital Strategy 2030** with specific emphasis to 'smart communities' – Slovenia), and countries where rural needs are sometimes insufficiently addressed into national strategies (e.g. Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina). Slovenia is the only country with a specific strategy to reinforce civil society and community action ([Strategy for the Development of the Non-Governmental Sector and Volunteering](#), 2023). In Bulgaria **National Development Programme** (by 2030) also identifies 'quality of life in rural areas' and 'local development' (including the CLLD programme) as priority areas. **Rural proofing** is implemented only in Finland and Spain. In Spain, rural proofing passed into a national law (27/2022) and at present, **9 out of the 17 Autonomous Communities incorporated** (or planned to) **rural proofing** in their regional legislation.

¹¹⁰ Note that rural heterogeneity is mirrored by a diverse set of national definitions of rural areas (Table 4) and rural typologies at national level.

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Despite this study does not analyse governance frameworks, it is possible to observe that structural and dedicated governance structures for rural development, are/might an enabling condition to promote integrated policies for rural areas. An example of this is the **Finnish Rural Council**, designed to be a cross-sectoral policy with people from the civil society, private and public sectors, or the **Spanish Secretary General for the Demographic Challenge**, under one single Ministry but dealing with depopulation at large. The Finnish case is more comparable to what a national implementation of the EU Rural Pact might be looking like¹¹¹. Additionally, selected countries differ strongly in terms of **governance and decentralisation levels**, and where competences stand in terms of rural development. Strong decentralisation is observed in Spain, for instance, where the Autonomous Regions have large competence into defining place-based approach to rural areas. On one hand, this allows for more place-based policies, on the other hand, it implies strong regional differences both in terms of policy design and implementation.

Results from EU policies in selected countries (CAP, Cohesion Policy)

Across countries, CAP is used to finance community-led innovation expressively via the LEADER programme, and more widely through the AKIS/EIP Operational Groups and innovation measures and investments. In relation to the **LEADER programme**, Spain is the one planning the highest **budget percentage** (10% of the EAFRD, i.e. twice the minimum allocation). All other countries are also above the minimum allocation. However, in terms of **LEADER population coverage**, Finland is the first country (100% of rural residents targeted), followed closely by Slovenia (90%), Bulgaria (80%) and less closely from Spain and Italy (both around 50% of rural population). This shows an important difference is because, in general, both Italy and Spain opted to finance less activities/communities but provide a larger budget. **Agricultural digitalisation** is key objective for Finland, whereas other CAP indicators (*on AKIS, rural businesses*) have important differences across Member States and would require a deeper analysis.

Only Finland, Italy and Spain (Galicia) designed specific measures for **Smart villages** in the CAP Strategic Plans. However, all countries allow them to finance them via other investment and cooperation measures (including through the LEADER programme). Only Finland, Italy and Spain allocate **clear budget and target indicators** for Smart Villages, whereas Slovenia define target indicators (no. of Smart Villages projects or strategies to be supported) but no actual budget). It is worth noting that **budget lines per Smart Village project/strategy vary significantly** across countries: Galicia (EUR 750/operation), Finland (EUR 166k), Italy (between EUR 26k and EUR 2.8 million). Overall, these data shows quite a diverse and cautious uptake of the Smart Village instrument in the 2023-27 period, mostly due to the fact that this instrument was first introduced in 2023 and Member States rely on different governance structures, experiences and capacities.

Within the **Cohesion Policy**, **CLLD and ITIs** are used across selected countries. However, the budget is less significant than the LEADER programme in absolute terms (confirming

¹¹¹ Rural Pact (2023). Making the Rural Pact happen in Member States. [rps-policy-briefing-rural-pacts-draft-230920_0.pdf](#)

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the EU Commission figures). Additionally, most data are not territorially targeted hence referring to non-urban areas but not specifically to rural, mountainous, sparsely populated areas and islands. Additionally, support to community-led local development is planned through the **EMFAF programme**. Remarkably, Slovenia has the highest percentual budget dedicated to CLLD (**36%** of total 2021-27 allocation). Other countries' allocation is around 7-10% of their total EMFAF budget. We can conclude that **EMFAF support community-led innovation in percentual terms more than the CAP and Cohesion Policy**. This is however not the case in absolute terms, as the overall EMFAF programme budget is only EUR 6.108 bln (compared to approximately EUR 778 bln for the CAP and Cohesion Policy together) [2021-27 period].

Results from the analysis SMART ERA Pilot Regions

SMART ERA Pilots cover a **diverse range of rural areas** (mountainous islands, sparsely populated) and **challenges** (agri-food, tourism, access to services and employment). As said above, their specific situation is sometimes quite different from the EU and national average, highlighting specific intra-national and intra-regional territorial divide.

Generally, it emerges that the most **recurring policy issues** faced by these rural areas are **demographic decline, ageing, brain drain** and **economic stagnation/decline**. Other key – and interconnected challenges – come the limited access to basic services (e.g. employment, transport, health), environmental degradation, and poor connectivity. In some cases, Pilot Regions describe those issues as **structural issues** lasting since the second half of the century, while in other cases, **new crises** (economic, sanitary, etc.) triggered or further hampered the vicious dynamics of these territories.

According to the analysis of Pilot Regions, actor groups which are the most affected by these challenges are **local communities, small farmers and rural entrepreneurs, young people and youth professionals, local authorities** in small rural areas and the **tourism sector**. Transition towards smart rural areas is a structured set of solutions to address those issues and bring forward benefit to the territory and local community.

Results from analysis of key players and interactions

Each Pilot Region provided an analysis of **main actor categories and interests** with respect to (smart) rural development, as well as the set of relations between stakeholders. As said, areas and dynamics are quite different across Pilot areas, however, an aggregate look of the results allows us to draw a few considerations.

First, actors with the highest resources and power to influence action are **governmental bodies and authorities, private sectors** (e.g. service providers and operators). For instance, the **Italian Pilot** perceive high power/influence from the dairy, farming and breeding sector and more generally agri-food value chains, whereas the **Spanish pilot** highlights the crucial role of the hospitality sector. In the **Finnish Pilot**, universities and other academic actors are perceived as having also large resources and power to influence rural development. In general, **rural residents** are felt like having a limited capability to influence

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the transition apart from the Spanish Pilot Region. In this rural area, **strong linkages and organisation of civil society** are felt as leading to increased power of the community to lead this change.

Overall, **incentives and barriers** to actor's behaviour are quite relevant. It emerges that **economic interests** are the main reason for different actor groups supporting (or not) smart rural development. This is certainly the case for the private sector and the entrepreneurial ecosystem, where better job opportunities and increased revenues linked to new forms of economic revitalisation in rural areas might counter any resistance. Opposition to change is also mentioned, for instance from the side of the agri-food sector and small producers which might feel incapable to adapt to change or digital transformation without the right support. **Authorities and governmental bodies** are mostly constrained to implement policy frameworks and strategies and to ensure electoral consensus for policy development. Showing the added value of smart rural development towards progressing is crucial to find strong partners.

A third important incentive to change is **cooperation and knowledge**. This is particularly the case of academic and research actors and media, seeking towards developing an in-depth understanding of rural dynamics. Collaborative projects – such as EU-funded projects – are a mean to facilitate cooperation. Finally, an incentive for the broader set of rural residents, youth and civil society organisations is to **increase quality of life and opportunities** (jobs, essential services). An improvement of the living conditions is essential to partner and obtain support from the local community.

In terms of **alliances**, the pictures are quite different across Pilots. Overall, **governmental and local authorities** have a central role in the interaction with most other stakeholders. On the contrary, **stakeholder groups do not always interact with one another**. Notably, this is the case for the tourism and agri-food sectors which both in Bulgaria and Spain do not seem to cooperate or share data with one another even though they might compete over the same resources (e.g. water, services) and/or cooperation might boost visibility and revenues for both (e.g. via rural tourism options). In the **Slovenian Pilot**, the presence of a network of already-existing projects and actors working on smart rural development seems facilitating the spread of this concept and its implementation.

Results on Policy Gaps

Legislative and strategic gaps are the most relevant polity gaps, as emerged from the Policy Audits. These gaps relate to i) the **actual lack** of legislative or strategic text addressing key areas of opportunities for smart rural areas (e.g. telemedicine, circular economy), ii) the **lack of reference to rural areas** in existing legislative or strategic text, iii) the **need to update and revise** strategies/legislative text on key topics related to innovation and smart rural areas as outdated.

The second and third most relevant gaps are related to the lack of **vertical/horizontal coordination** (e.g. gaps in multi-level governance, partnership principle, cross-sectoral cooperation) and lack of **data** for monitoring, assessing and progressing on the development

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of smart rural areas (e.g. on tourism, community transport usage). Of the mapped gaps, some are cross-cutting, and others are more sector-related. It is therefore not surprising a large number of gaps in the tourism sector as this is addressed by several SMART ERA Pilot Regions.

Figure 27 Policy gaps identified by SMART ERA Pilot Regions. Source: Own elaboration.

Results from the analysis of Policy Options

SMART ERA Pilot Regions identified a total amount of **19 Policy Options** (of which 13 new instruments and 6 revisioning existing instruments). These Policy Options are intended to drive the **smart transition of rural areas**, over one or multiple areas. Tourism is the sector mostly targeted by SMART ERA Policy Options, as key sector for many of the project's Pilot Regions. Other Policy Options are fairly distributed across eight other areas (Figure 28).

Figure 29 describes the innovative approach of proposed Policy Options. The highest number of identified Policy Options suggest introducing innovation at the level of the **governance system**, followed by innovation in **legislation** and **use/development of a digital platform** for data sharing, using and interoperability leading to better policy development. The detailed description of Policy Options can be found in Annex 2.

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Figure 28 Count of SMART ERA Policy Options by Topic/Area. Source: Own elaboration

Figure 29 Count of SMART ERA Policy Options by Innovation Type. Source: Own elaboration

6. Conclusions

This report investigates the linkages between policies and smart rural communities in Europe. Notably, it first looks at the EU-level policies for community-led rural innovation and then it performs six in-depth country and regional analysis.

This national and regional policy analysis allows us to identify the policy contexts and specific dynamics underlying rural development in selected areas. A number of case-specific conclusions as well as findings from the comparative analysis of case studies have been identified under the 'Key Results' chapter.

This study allows us to identify some commonalities and policy gaps which are not case specific, hence having relevance for wider EU policy development, in light of the post-2027 EU budget negotiations.

This study has futural limitations, which are linked to data accessibility. For the future, we would recommend develop more close analysis of CLLD budget in the 2021-2027 Cohesion Policy, as this – comparatively to the LEADER programme – lacks a more in-depth analysis. Additionally, another avenue of research would be to investigate more closely the early results from the implementation of Smart Villages projects in the current programming period.

This study concludes with a set of Policy Options for smart rural areas. Spanning across sectors, these Policy Options provide concrete inspiration for supporting community-rural innovation in Europe, based on ideas and discussions of SMART ERA stakeholders.

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Annex 1. EU sectoral policies relevant to SMART ERA smartness dimensions

Improved social care and services and participation in decision-making

Table 31 Key EU policies in improved social care and services, and participation in decision making

Policy name	Aims to
Article 168 (1) of the TFEU	Set a high-level human health protection as a fundamental principle in the formulation and execution of all EU policies
Right to Petition (Art 277 TFEU)	Bolster citizen engagement in decision-making by allowing individuals to raise concerns directly with the EU Parliament
EU's health Strategy (2010-20)	Strengthen global health governance through enhanced international cooperation and partnerships
EU Better Regulation Guidelines and Toolbox	Improve the quality and transparency of EU law-making by ensuring evidence-based policymaking and consultation
Have your Say Portal	Enables citizens and stakeholders to contribute to EU policymaking by giving feedback on legislative initiatives
EU Pillar of Social Rights (2017) and its Action Plan (2021)	Set of principles and rights to support well-functioning labour markets and welfare systems
EU Care Strategy (2022)	Ensure high-quality, affordable and accessible care services for care receivers while also enhancing their conditions
European Social Fund + (2021-2027)	Supports employment, education, and social inclusion, focus on reducing inequalities and promoting equal opportunities

Source: Own elaboration.

Education

Table 32 Key EU policies in education

Policy name	Aims to
EU Charter of Fundamental Rights	Enshrine fundamental rights, including the right to education and vocational training, when implementing EU law
ET2020 Framework (2009-20)	Promote EU-wide cooperation to enhance education and training systems through lifelong learning and employability
EU Skills Agenda (2020)	Improve skills development to support green and digital transitions, boost competitiveness, and ensure social fairness
EU Pact for Skills (2020)	Foster public-private partnerships to promote upskilling and reskilling across key industrial ecosystems
2030 Strategic Framework for Education and Training (2021)	Support inclusive, high-quality education and training systems to deliver the EU Education Area and promote lifelong learning
EU Education Area 2025	Create a unified European Education Area by 2025, ensuring access to high-quality education and making learning mobility a reality for all
Erasmus+ (2021-27)	Foster learning mobility, cooperation, and inclusion in education, training, youth, and sport across Europe

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European Social Fund+ (2021-27)	Support employment, education, and social inclusion, with a focus on reducing inequalities and promoting equal opportunities
Digital Europe Programme (2021-27)	Accelerate digital transformation in the EU by funding projects related to digital skills, infrastructure, digital technologies
Horizon Europe (2021-27)	Fund research and innovation to tackle global challenges and strengthen the EU's scientific and technological bases
EU Talent Booster Mechanism (2023)	Attract, retain, and develop talent in regions facing demographic and workforce challenges to strengthen regional competitiveness

Source: Own elaboration.

Sustainable Mobility

Table 33 Key EU policies in mobility

Policy name	Aims to
Connecting Europe Facility (2021-27)	Support high-performing, sustainable, and efficiently interconnected trans-EU networks in transport, energy, and digital services
TEN-T	Build an EU-wide multimodal transport network to improve connectivity, efficiency, and sustainability
Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (2013, 2019)	Promote sustainable mobility and improve quality of life in urban areas
Green Deal (2019)	Make the EU climate-neutral by 2050 through sustainable economic transformation
EU Urban Mobility Framework (2021)	Guide cities in developing cleaner, more accessible, and efficient urban transport systems
Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy (2021)	Set the path for greener, smarter, and more resilient transport across the EU to meet climate neutrality by 2050
Fit for 55 Package (2021)	Reduce EU GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030

Source: Own elaboration.

Tourism

Table 34 Key EU policies in transport

Policy name	Aims to
Art 195 of the TFEU (2007)	Support the competitiveness of the tourism sector by promoting cooperation between Member States and complementing national policies
Nature Directives (1979, 1992)	Provide the legal framework for the conservation of Europe's most valuable and threatened species & habitats
EU industrial strategy (2020, 2021)	Strengthen EU industrial competitiveness and autonomy, supporting green and digital transitions
EU Biodiversity Strategy (2020)	Protect nature and reverse the degradation of ecosystems by 2030
EU strategy for adaptation to climate change (2021)	Enhance the EU's resilience by improving preparedness and response to the impacts of climate change
EU Tourism Agenda 2030 (2022)	Provide a roadmap for the green and digital transition of EU tourism, enhancing resilience and sustainability

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Nature Restoration Law (2023)	Require Member States to restore degraded ecosystems and biodiversity across land and sea
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Agri-food and circular economy

Table 35 Key EU policies in agri-food and circular economy

Policy name	Aims to
Common Agricultural Policy	Support farmers, ensure food security, promote rural development, and encourage socio-environmental sustainability
Nature Directives (1979, 1992)	Provide the legal framework for the conservation of Europe's most valuable and threatened species & habitats
Packaging and Package Waste Directive (1994, 2022)	Reduce the environmental impact of packaging and promote recycling and reuse.
General Food Law (2002)	Establish the general principles and requirements of food law to ensure food safety and protect public health.
EU Waste Framework Directive (2008, 2018)	Set the basic concepts and definitions related to waste management and promote waste prevention, reuse, and recycling
Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive (2009)	Reduces risks and impacts of pesticide use on human health and the environment
Food Information for Consumers (2011)	Ensures clear, accurate, and transparent food labelling for consumers in the EU
Bioeconomy Strategy (2012)	Promotes the use of renewable biological resources for sustainable production in various sectors
Plant health rules (2016)	Protects plant health in the EU by preventing the introduction and spread of harmful pests
Organic Farming (2018)	Set rules for organic production, labelling, and control to support sustainable agriculture and consumer trust
Single Use Plastic Directive (2019)	Reduce the impact of certain plastic products on the environment, especially marine litter
Farm to Fork Strategy (2020)	Build a fair, healthy, and environmentally-friendly food system across the EU
Biodiversity Strategy (2020)	Halts biodiversity loss and restores ecosystems across the EU by 2030
EU Green Deal (2019)	Set the overarching roadmap to make the EU climate-neutral by 2050 while promoting sustainability
Circular economy Action Plan (2020)	Make sustainable products the norm in the EU, reduce waste, and promote circular business models
EU Climate Law (2021)	Legally bind the EU to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 and reduce emissions by at least 55% by 2030
EU Vision on Food and Agriculture (2025)	Set future goals for sustainable food systems and resilient agriculture

Source: Own elaboration.

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Digital and women/youth entrepreneurship

Table 36 Key EU policies in digital and women/youth entrepreneurship

Policy name	Aims to
New EU Innovation Agenda (2022)	Drive innovation-led growth across the EU, with a focus on deep tech, scaling start-ups, and regional innovation ecosystems
InvestEU (2021-27)	Mobilise public and private investment to support sustainable growth, innovation, and jobs across the EU
European Social Fund+ (2021-27)	Support employment, social inclusion, education, and skills development across the EU
Digital Markets Act (2022)	Ensure fair and open digital markets by regulating gatekeeper platforms to foster competition
Artificial Intelligence Act (2024)	Establish harmonised rules for safe and trustworthy AI deployment across the EU
Digital Services Act (2022)	Modernise the digital single market by increasing transparency and accountability of online platforms
EU Competitiveness Compass (2025)	Provide a framework to monitor and enhance the EU's industrial and technological competitiveness
EU Startup and Scale up strategy (2025)	Support the growth of startups and scale-ups through better access to finance, markets, and talent
EU Innovation Act (under development)	Streamline innovation policies and foster cutting-edge technologies in Europe

Source: Own elaboration.

Annex 2. SMART ERA Policy Options

This Annex summarises the Policy Options which have been identified by the SMART ERA Pilot Regions to transition towards smart rural communities. Whereas these Policy Options are specific to the needs and challenges of SMART ERA Pilot Regions, they can be adapted and replicated in other rural areas. This means that **their potential benefits are likely to be scaled up** in other rural territories.

Policy Options for the Devetaki Plateau Pilot (Bulgaria)

Policy Option #1	Telemedicine for Personalised Rural Healthcare
Gaps Addressed	Lack of medical services; Ageing population.
Type	Create a New Instrument
Description	The lack of regular medical services is a major issue in rural areas. The region previously had a visiting doctor, but with their passing, no regular medical services exist. The absence of regular medical services forces residents to travel long distances for basic healthcare. This leads to untreated chronic illnesses, lower quality of life, and increased reliance on family or informal caregivers. Telemedicine and mobile health services could provide remote healthcare support, giving residents access to medical consultations without requiring travel to distant urban centers. These measures should target the early diagnosis and prevention of sicknesses and crises, whereas in-depth treatment could be pursued in specialised centres in urban or other areas.
Implementing body & level	National and local levels.
Impacts and Effects	Regular healthcare services in rural areas; Early diagnosis and prevention; Right to stay.

Policy Option #2	Community-Driven Transport Service
Gaps Addressed	Limited and unreliable public transport; unaffordability of private transport; Poverty trap.
Type	Create a New Instrument
Description	Poor public transport restricts access to jobs, education, and medical care, deepening economic and social exclusion. The elderly and low-income residents suffer the most, as they cannot afford private transport. This issue traps people into poverty they cannot access quality jobs, education, and medical care. A community-driven transport service using shared minivans, ride-sharing apps, or an on-demand rural transport system could significantly improve mobility. This smart solution should go hand in hand with investment in road infrastructure and connectivity.
Implementing body & level	Local authorities; Support from National governments.

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Impacts and Effects	Increased economic and social well-being; Better access to jobs, education and medical care;
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Policy Option #3 Community Digital Literacy Training	
Gaps Addressed	Business Development; Digital Literacy and Education; Teleworking opportunities.
Type	Create a New Instrument
Description	This Smart Solution seeks opportunities to untap the potential of digitalisation both for business development and residents. In this area, the slow development of rural broadband rollout is often worsened by low digital literacy. A two-fold community digital literacy training should be developed to: i) support local businesses to engage in e-commerce and remote work, ii) encourage rural residents to adopt online services (e.g. e-commerce, telemedicine, educational opportunities).
Implementing body & level	National level (integration via policies and strategies); Local level (for piloting and providing technical/other forms of support).
Impacts and Effects	Increased economic and job opportunities, including via teleworking; enhanced business outreach, commercialisation and access to specialised workers and/or niche markets; Increased access to online services and knowledge for local residents.

Policy Option #4 Smart Eco-Tourism and Farming Incentives	
Gaps Addressed	Small-farms steady decline leading to land degradation and natural risks; tourism attractiveness; Low access to capital for high-risk rural projects.
Type	Create a New instrument
Description	Few job opportunities exist in the region, forcing younger generations to migrate to urban centres. The region has eco-tourism potential, but poor infrastructure, data collection and marketing development. This policy option aims at creating economic incentives for eco-tourism and agri-businesses, promoting local crafts and organic farming through e-commerce, collection and processing of data on tourist flow and feedback, and modernising tourism infrastructure as a whole.
Implementing body & level	Local level
Impacts and Effects	Counter youth brain drain; revitalisation through sustainable tourism opportunities; new job opportunities and poverty reduction; improved natural capital and biodiversity.

Policy Options for the East Herzegovina Pilot (BiH)

Policy Option #1 Smart Community-Led Rural Tourism	
Gaps Addressed	Lack of definition and measures on specific forms of rural tourism; encourage farms to declare rural tourism activities and monitor trends.
Type	Create a New Instrument

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Description	Include a new definition of ‘Smart Community-Led Rural Tourism- in the current legislative framework encompassing emerging rural tourism categories such as excursion tourism and agritourism. In complementarity with this, allocated specific budget to these activities throughout the Ministry of Trade and Tourism and launch a campaign to register farms dealing with forms of smart community-led rural tourism. Additionally, Law on Hospitality of the Republic of Srpska should be amended to include new categories of hospitality establishments that would support service providers in rural communities, such as “tasting rooms” which would enable local producers to enhance their offerings and create new tourist experiences tailored to rural settings. Currently, these categories do not exist in the legislation, making it difficult for certain rural tourism offers to be formally recognised.
Implementing body & level	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of the Republic of Srpska; Ministry of Trade and Tourism of Republic of Srpska
Impacts and Effects	This Policy Option would expand market opportunities and help diversifying income of farmers dealing with rural tourism. Knock-on benefits would reach the tourists – gaining from enhanced tourism packages and products, and local communities.

Policy Option #2	E-Visitor System
Gaps Addressed	Facilitate tourist arrivals; simplify administrative procedures; provide real-time data; reduce grey market in tourism value chain
Type	Create a New Instrument
Description	E-Visitor is a central and specialised free electronic system that connects all tourism organizations in one place. One of the main tasks of the system is to provide insight into daily tourist traffic, including guest check-ins and check-outs, maintain an up-to-date database of accommodation units and hosts, and track and process statistical data related to arrivals and departures, types of accommodation, and destinations. It also enables accurate control of tourist tax collection, all with the goal of maximizing revenue from tourism and service activities and identifying areas for improvement for the upcoming season. The E-Visitor obligor is a natural or legal person, i.e., the owner of a property being rented, and a single obligor may have multiple properties.
Implementing body & level	National level and Republic of Srpska
Impacts and Effects	The purpose of E-Visitor is the consolidation of data on accommodation service providers, creating an up-to-date unified database, guest check-in and check-out by accommodation providers, and calculation and control of tourist tax collection. The introduction of the eVisitor system would strengthen compliance with existing laws on foreign visitor registration, tourist taxes, and accommodation standards. It would improve data collection, reporting, and enforcement, making related policies more effective. It would also help reducing the grey market, which currently is estimated to account for around 50% of accommodation services. It would also ensure the registration of foreign guests, as required by the Law on Foreigners ("Official Gazette of BiH", Nos. 88/2015, 34/2021, and 63/2023) and other legal and sub-legal acts regulating the registration of foreign

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	visitors. Currently, this is not enforced, as many foreign guests stay in unregistered accommodations and are therefore not officially recorded.
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Policy Option #3 Community-Led Management of Protected Areas	
Gaps Addressed	Insufficient management capacity of public managers for protected areas (beyond basic needs); Lack of dedicated funding for restoration, reconstruction, and valorisation of both natural and cultural heritage; Limited integration of smart, community-led initiatives and digital platforms for tourism and rural development; Fragmented multi-level governance; Underutilisation of heritage sites; Sustainability and Area Preservation.
Type	Create a New Instrument
Description	Currently, Republika Srpska has 34 protected areas. However, entities in charge of the management of these areas neither have the capacity nor the mandate to manage these areas beyond tasks such as clearing land, maintaining access roads, and similar activities. This duty is currently covered by public enterprise Šume Republike Srpske Почетна or local municipalities/cities. All protected areas face financial difficulties and are largely unsustainable. In most cases, organising tourist activities is very difficult, due to bureaucratic obstacles and the lack of interest from the administrators. The issue also concerns cultural heritage under protection, which in most cases is ruined and at risk of further decay. Institutions often avoid taking responsibility, and there is no dedicated funding line for restoration, reconstruction, or revitalisation. Some of these sites are included in tourism offerings, but their touristic valorisation has not been sufficiently developed, meaning they cannot be properly presented to visitors. According to this Policy Option, the management of some protected areas should be delegated to stakeholders and communities, based on the establishment of a ranger service and management plans. Management units should be defined, and in some cases, tourism organizations should be responsible, particularly for protected landscapes of touristic importance.
Implementing body & level	National and local authorities
Impacts and Effects	There is no negative impact for the current managers, as this management was imposed on them and in most cases represents a burden. Conversely, other stakeholders would benefit significantly: local communities would gain from improved economic opportunities, tourists would have access to better experiences, and tourism organizations and stakeholders managing the sites would be able to more effectively promote and valorise the protected areas and cultural heritage.

Policy Option #4 Tourism Membership Fee	
Gaps Addressed	Lack of funding for tourism promotion
Type	Create a New Instrument

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Description	<p>In Republika Srpska, over 90% of tourism organization revenues come from tourist accommodation taxes. In most cases, these revenues are not enough to finance significant development or promotional activities in the tourism sector. As a result, the work of tourism organizations is largely limited to light activities in information centres, with minimal promotional engagement and no concrete development initiatives. To address this issue, it is necessary to introduce funding through a tourism membership fee, as well as reorganise the operations of tourism organizations. All entities generating direct or indirect income from hospitality or other tourism services, or performing tourism-related activities, are required to become members and should pay a membership fee. A legal or natural person that has its headquarters, residence, branch, facility, or establishment where services are provided within the territory of a local tourism organization established in accordance with the law regulating the system of tourism associations, and that permanently or seasonally generates income from providing hospitality services, tourism-related services, or conducts an activity that benefits from tourism-or whose income is influenced by tourism- shall pay a membership fee to the respective tourism organization. At least 20% of collected membership fees must be allocated to the development of tourism products. Furthermore, the boards of these organizations should include representatives of tourism businesses that contribute the most to municipal/city revenues in Republika Srpska, ensuring that key stakeholders are actively involved in decision-making and development planning. <i>This policy is already implemented in Croatia Zakon o članarinama u turističkim zajednicama - Zakon.hr and in some parts of Bosnia and Herzegovina, for ex. Sarajevo kanton (Official Gazzete Kanton Sarajevo, no 31/17 and 34/17).</i></p>
Implementing body & level	Government of Republic of Srpska and the Ministry for trade and tourism Republic of Srpska
Impacts and Effects	Primarily, tourism organizations would gain a stable and predictable funding source for development, marketing, and promotional activities and tourists would experience better services, more organised tourism offerings, and enhanced cultural and natural experiences. Additionally, local communities would benefit from improved destination promotion, increased visitor numbers, and potential economic growth, and potential improvement in long-term sustainability and valorisation of natural and cultural heritage.

Policy Options for the Northern Ostrobothnia Pilot (Finland)

Policy Option #1	Regional Competence Hub for Commercialisation and Funding Readiness
Gaps Addressed	Lack of support for SMEs and micro-enterprises (commercialisation, IP protection, funding readiness); Convert research excellence into market-ready innovations.
Type	Create a New Instrument
Description	Establish a regional competence hub that provides targeted support in commercialisation, IP management, and funding strategy. Services would be embedded in existing regional structures (e.g., OIA members) and tailored for micro-enterprises, spin-offs, and RDI actors.

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Implementing body & level	Regional innovation intermediaries (e.g., BusinessOulu, university innovation services), coordinated with Business Finland (regional/national level).
Impacts and Effects	Improved SME innovation outcomes, greater ERDF absorption, strengthened regional innovation ecosystems. It would also boost the effectiveness of ERDF Priority on Innovation and S3 implementation. Increases leverage of national and EU research funding.

Policy Option #2	AI-Supported Climate Alignment in ERDF Funding Decisions
Gaps Addressed	Do not do Significant Harm principle inconsistently applied in ERDF project evaluation, slowing decisions and risking non-compliance
Type	Adjust Existing Policy
Description	This Policy Tool would be aimed at the development and implementation of an AI-based tool to screen ERDF funding applications against North Ostrobothnia's Climate Roadmap and do not do significant harm criteria. It would ensure transparent and consistent scoring across sectors.
Implementing body & level	National and EU programme authorities (funding bodies); tool to be developed and maintained by an independent technology provider (national/EU level).
Impacts and Effects	Faster and fairer funding decisions; stronger climate coherence; better alignment between ERDF, climate neutrality targets, and land-use planning. Provides a model for other EU regions.

Policy Options for the Valle di Sole Pilot (Italy)

Policy Option #1	Binding Requirement for Public Data Granularity
Gaps Addressed	Lack of publicly accessible data regarding fund absorption and implementation outcomes; Insufficient transparency in the dissemination of interim results and actual spending levels.
Type	Adjust Existing Policy
Description	Introduce a binding requirement for the Regional Managing Authority and implementing entities to publish quarterly updates on i) Committed and disbursed funds; ii) Types and numbers of beneficiaries; iii) Intermediate performance indicators (e.g., hectares affected, jobs created, young farmers supported, etc.).
Implementing body & level	Rural Development Policy Service of the Autonomous Province of Trento. Oversight by the Monitoring Committee of the Complement to Rural Development Programming (CSR).
Impacts and Effects	Increased administrative burden could be mitigated via digital tools and simplified reporting systems, but it would allow to have more accurate information on actual distribution of funds to beneficiaries, including allowing to identify synergies with other policies (particularly, environmental and climate policies, Cohesion measures for rural/mountain areas under the SNAI).

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Policy Option #2		Disaggregated National Observatory for Rural Areas
Gaps Addressed		Absence of disaggregated data specific to specific rural areas (e.g. Valle di Sole) within national monitoring platforms (in particular the OpenCoesione); Limited availability of updated information for the post-2020 programming period.
Type		Adjust Existing Policy
Description		Enhance OpenCoesione by integrating a dedicated monitoring module for territories at Eurostat's Local Area Unit level, providing: i) Disaggregated financial data on projects; ii) Territorial socio-demographic indicators; iii) Performance indicators reflecting access to services, demographic dynamics, and economic trends.
Implementing body & level		National level: Agency for Territorial Cohesion; Local level: Support from local, provincial and regional authorities.
Impacts and Effects		Increased monitoring of targeted interventions in marginal and rural territories for all levels of government; Improved policy design for Cohesion Policy; Reinforces the alignment with other existing policies (e.g. SNAI, sub-national level strategies, CAP and Cohesion Policy interventions);

Policy Option #3		Digital Investment Platform for the Forest Value Chain
Gaps Addressed		Absence of transparent data on the allocation and use of funds within the forestry sector; Monitoring tools (SIGFAT, VAS) are technically sound but not accessible to non-specialist stakeholders.
Type		Create a New Instrument
Description		Develop a publicly accessible digital platform for forestry-related investments, including: i) GIS-based mapping of funded projects; ii) Environmental impact indicators (e.g., biodiversity indices, carbon sequestration metrics); iii) Integration with existing tools (SIGFAT, Strategic Environmental Assessment).
Implementing body & level		Regional level: department of Forests, Autonomous Province of Trento; Technical support: APPA and ISPRA for environmental validation.
Impacts and Effects		Enhanced management and valorisation of forestland; Enhanced transparency and ecosystem service management; Re-establishment of forest-based value chains.

Policy Option #4		Community-Led Sustainable Transition Action
Gaps Addressed		Limited engagement of local stakeholders in the implementation and evaluation of sustainable development actions; Lack of disaggregated and lower-level data.
Type		Adjust Existing Policy
Description		Institutionalise participatory mechanisms and improve communication in the Provincial Strategy for Sustainable Development by: i) organising annual public sustainability forums; ii) publishing interactive reports and dashboards with updated indicators (climate, biodiversity, education, youth engagement).

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Implementing body & level	Regional level: coordination Unit for Sustainable Development, Province of Trento; Supported by APPA, academic institutions, and civil society organisations.
Impacts and Effects	Greater engagement of various stakeholder types, including marginalised actors, in sustainable transition; Institutions gain greater social legitimacy and alignment with Agenda 2030; Strengthened public engagement in rural development policies.

Policy Option #5 Youth Engagement and Strategic Plans	
Gaps Addressed	Limited involvement of youth population; Counter youth outmigration and brain drain; Low transparency and inclusivity in programme planning processes.
Type	Adjust Existing Policy
Description	Mandate the publication of annual reports disaggregated by youth zone (Upper/Lower Valle di Sole); Facilitate participatory planning by involving youth councils and community groups in agenda-setting processes.
Implementing body & level	Local level: community of Valle di Sole; Provincial level: department for Youth Policies, in partnership with the Franco Demarchi Foundation.
Impacts and Effects	Greater involvement of youth (aged 11-35); Increased social and cultural revitalisation in the local community; Better identification of capacity needs (e.g. digitalisation, skills).

Policy Options for the Šmarje/Padna Pilot (Slovenia)

Policy Option #1 National Support Programme for Digital Mobility Services in Rural Areas	
Gaps Addressed	Lack of tailored support for small-scale digital infrastructure and mobility solutions within existing rural development funding schemes.
Type	Create a New Instrument
Description	A national support programme providing technical assistance, funding, and mentoring for local communities piloting digital mobility and smart village solutions. This could be integrated within rural development and innovation policy.
Implementing body & level	Ministry of Digital Transformation (national), in collaboration with the Ministry of Agriculture and local municipalities (local/regional).
Impacts and Effects	Rural communities gain access to mobility solutions, digital inclusion improves, rural youth and elderly benefit; Increased inter-ministerial coordination and local capacity building in mobility; Reduced pressure on urban centres by improving rural liveability; Supports green transition, circular economy, social cohesion, and digitalisation agendas.

Policy Options for the Sóller/Tramuntana Pilot (Spain)

Policy Option #1 Smart Tourism Carrying Capacity Measure	
Gaps Addressed	Tourism oversaturation in specific areas; Poor monitoring of tourist flows; Conflict between tourism and local residents; Lack of residents' involvement in sustainable tourism

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Type	Create a New Instrument
Description	Establish visitor limits in heritage, low-emission, and sensitive areas of Sóller based on seasonal visitor counts. Introduce technological infrastructure (sensors, data platforms, monitoring and management tools) to track and manage visitor flow. Complement with awareness campaigns, communication initiatives, and community training programs to encourage local engagement and sustainable tourism practices. The aim is to reduce congestion, improve residents' quality of life, and support long-term tourism sustainability.
Implementing body & level	Local government of Sóller, in coordination with regional tourism authorities and local stakeholders (especially commerce, culture/heritage and HORECA). Implementation at the municipal and regional level , with potential guidance from national tourism sustainability frameworks.
Impacts and Effects	Improved quality of life, reduced traffic and services congestion; increased cultural and natural preservation. In terms of policy, this option would enhance the integration with sustainable tourism strategies, low-emission zone, and cultural heritage protection measures. It would require further adjustments in mobility, parking, and local infrastructure planning (like ZBE) to manage visitor flow. Businesses may adapt operational hours, booking systems, or alternative service models to accommodate visitor limits.

Policy Option #2	Expanded Local Mechanism for Tourism Circularity
Gaps Addressed	Expand Law 3/22 (Tourism Circular Law)
Type	Adjust Existing Policy
Description	The current 3% threshold in for local product sourcing (Law 3/22) is too low to significantly impact local agriculture or strengthen food supply chains. Thus, the rule risks being more symbolic than transformative, with limited effect on farmer income, generational renewal, or resilience of local food systems. The monitoring system falls short on tracking effectively the compliance or measuring the socioeconomic/environmental impact. This measure should amend Law 3/22 to raise the minimum share of local products sourced by tourist establishments (hotels, restaurants, and accommodations) to 10–15%. A phased timeline is recommended (e.g., 5% by 2026, 10% by 2028, 15% by 2030) to allow businesses and producers to adapt. This should be complemented with support measures for local farmers and tourism operators (training, logistics, digitalization, cooperative B2B platforms), along with a reliable compliance verification mechanism (audits and product origin certifications).
Implementing body & level	Regional Government of the Balearic Islands – legislative change and monitoring; Consell de Mallorca and municipalities – enforcement and awareness campaigns; Farmer cooperatives and hospitality associations – operational support and coordination.
Impacts and Effects	Strengthened credibility and tangible impact of Law 3/22 on tourism circularity, local agri-food development, jobs and resident nutritional health; Potential market advantage ('authentic Balearic products') and positioning as sustainable tourism hub; Greater alignment with sustainability and tourism plan; Potential synergies with Law 2/16 to finance sectors' adaption and logistic hubs and with Smart Villages.

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Policy Option #3		Multi-sectoral Platform for Governance and Policy Innovation
Gaps Addressed	Fragmented coordination between tourism, agriculture, commerce and cultural sector; Top-down decision-making hindering innovation and co-creation; Missed opportunities and effort duplication; Lack of cross-sectoral trust.	
Type	Create a New Instrument	
Description	Establish an obligatory governance council including key local stakeholders (municipality, tourism businesses, farmers' associations, cultural entities, civil society). The council would hold quarterly meetings, ensure transparent, digital documentation of decisions, and serve as a forum for co-creation of policy initiatives. Potential duties of the council: i) Integrate structured innovation processes: pilot programs, ideation workshops, and collaborative testing of new tourism, mobility, and rural development solutions; ii) Facilitate knowledge exchange, digitalization of operations, and experimentation with sustainable practices; iii) Align tourism and rural development policies with both communities' needs and innovative, scalable solutions.	
Implementing body & level	Local level: Municipality of Sóller, with support from Consell de Mallorca; Regional level: Integration with the Serra de Tramuntana Consortium and Balearic Government for coherence with regional policies.	
Impacts and Effects	Local businesses, residents, cultural institutions, policymakers, and innovators gain from coordinated strategies, shared resources, and opportunities for pilot projects, resulting in better policy design, monitoring and delivery.	